

Comparative Assessment of Media Supply and Production in Ten EU Countries

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INTRODUCTION

The Deliverable 4.4. summarises main conceptual and empirical issues on media supply and production. The Deliverable is a product of the comparative analysis, combining systemic aspects of media supply and media professionals' views on production. The analysis follows a conceptual framework that aims to understand what factors within media systems and journalistic practices support democratic participation. Based on an in-depth research process, this report explores the strengths and weaknesses of different media sectors (Public Service Media, commercial, and non-profit) in their ability to inform and engage citizens.

The findings, derived from extensive data collection and comparative analysis, reveal critical trends concerning the economic, professional, legal, political, and cultural factors that define the contemporary media environment. These factors were identified from a vast amount of data collected in Task 4.1 and Deliverable 4.2, which mapped the news media landscape across 10 EU countries.

A methodological framework and design were developed in co-operation with other working packages (further referred to as WPs), particularly WP2 and WP3, in months 13-15. It is worth to add that compared to the proposal, the WP4 Deliverables, including the Deliverable 4.4. underwent efficient and sound restructuring in order to meet the project requirements and cope with a challenge of shortage of comparable data. A series of online meetings with country teams served to clarify the research protocol, addressing specific issues related to anonymization, challenges in recruiting journalists and chief editors, and project deadlines. Country teams conducted interviewees in months 16-20 and completed transcriptions and translations of interviews in months 19-20. Country reports were accomplished in months 20-21 and the final report was completed in months 21-22. Utilizing the country reports from Deliverable 4.3 and English transcripts of interviews conducted by country teams, the WP4 team performed a deep content analysis. They then derived conclusions from this analysis, using the four established sectors of analysis as a framework.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The role of the news media in supporting democratic aspirations of a society is important at the level of media systems, as well as news production. Democratic participation is both deliberative and practical: it manifests through a daily practice of staying informed, engaging in public discourse, and taking action to influence policy and political decisions. In this sense, journalism could serve as a crucial bridge, connecting professional integrity and responsibility with a society's democratic goals. The Deliverable 4.4. summarizes the main conceptual and empirical issues regarding media supply and production, focusing on their impact on democratic participation in 10 EU countries. The analysis combines a systemic perspective (public, commercial, and non-profit sectors of media systems) with news production practices. This research explores media production from a particular angle of five groups of factors: economic, professional, legal/regulatory, political, and cultural.

Taking into consideration economic factors, the analysis has shown that the press sector seems to be most vulnerable both in terms of ownership concentration and financial stability, while the audiovisual sector suffers mostly from a high or medium-level ownership concentration in a number of countries. Interviewed journalists and media producers from several countries observed the phenomenon of structural elitism of journalism and a complex impact of the Big Tech on media business models. The analysis of professional/journalistic factors has shown that exposure of journalistic standards proved to be highest in the PSM sector, while in the commercial sector, it varied across countries depending on a professional stance on self-regulation. Interviewed journalists and media producers confirmed differences between countries with a guiding role of self-regulatory codes of conduct or ethics (Germany, Estonia, Slovenia) and countries without pivotal role of codified rules (Poland, Italy). Studying of legal/regulatory factors revealed that legal and regulatory safeguards concerning PSM in many countries do not guarantee impartial, non-discriminatory and fair appointment procedures that would translate into professional and impartial PSM governance. As regards the commercial and non-profit sectors, interviewed journalists and media producers perceived state support and subsidies, including a more focused distribution of resources, as a necessary solution for targeting crisis in media business. The analysis has also shown that political factors remain of utmost importance for all sectors, and in some cases decisive about their viability. In views of most interviewed journalists and media producers, political participation in general manifests through participation in election, electoral politics and voting, and thus extensive electoral coverage in general supports democratic participation. At the same time, some interviewees pointed also to the processual character of participation, that may be strengthened through emancipation and inclusion, and weakened through exclusion of topics, problems and groups. With regard to social/cultural factors, the comparative analysis has shown that the third sector generally benefits from: legal recognition, stable financial support from public sources, institutional framework, transparency and adherence to journalistic standards. The interviewed journalists and media producers observed that PSM still play a leading role in providing cultural diversity, both because of legal or social obligations, and greater likelihood of diverse newsrooms.

These findings combining results from Task 4.1 and Task 4.2. help to define strengths and weaknesses of each sector in a given economic, professional/journalistic, legal/regulatory,

political and social/cultural dimension, identifying trends and differences between countries within Task 4.4.

1. A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Despite communicative abundance, access to information plays a principal role in democratic participation in views of citizens (Silver, L., Fagan, M., Huang, Ch. and Clancy, L., 2025). Media systems and media organisations still constitute important sites for representation and explanation of social world and politics, they continue to provide space for formation of public opinion and democratic participation. At the same time, media systems, once composed of legacy media, underwent hybridization, dissociation and absorption by platform infrastructures, business models and logics (Chadwick, 2017; Zuboff 2015). Media systems can still be seen as macrostructures, in which media entities, news creators and their news operations are arranged together in a particular way, due to (but not only) the impact of media and communication policies and other factors (demographic, cultural, political, etc.). In this sense, media systems still exhibit some degree of autonomy as they are constituted and reproduced through special professional practices, including news production and certain professional culture (Luhmann, 2000; Alexander, 2016). Yet, the provision of news and information is increasingly fragmented, elusive, delivered in many forms, formats and combinations of media and communication networks. Media systems crystallize, on the one hand, around the legacy media, that have existed before the advent of the internet. On the other hand, they operate through networks and contents generated by content producers, including platform operators and Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Building on numerous scholarly attempts to describe and categorise media systems (Siebert, Peterson and Schramm, 1963; Humphreys, 1996; Hallin and Mancini, 2004; Humprecht et al., 2022; Fuchs, 2024; Ots et al., 2024), the Deliverable 4.4. aims to provide a comparative framework for combining the analysis of systemic media factors with media production in order to understand impact on democratic participation. This comparative analysis seeks to answer following questions: What factors support democratic participation at the level of media systems and journalistic production? What are the strengths and weaknesses of different media sectors and at the national level in this regard? What similarities and differences can be observed at a supranational European level?

Media systems are institutionally composed of a number of media outlets and entities providing the news to the general public. From a European perspective, such entities function in three segments of the media landscape that have different mandate, operational mode and represent a different potential for political participation: PSM (Public Service Media), commercial media and non-profit sector. This composition of a given media system, particularly with regard to the role of public service and non-profit sectors, seems to be relatively unique in a global context. At the same time, in face of global restructuring and growing dependency on digital platforms, the three sectors are affected by various systemic factors that decisively impact pro-democratic media role and participation. In an attention-driven economy, news and journalistic content or sources for

that content, are increasingly created outside traditional media organisations and newsrooms. Political communication is centered on social media, while individual influencers, YouTubers or TikTokers amplify issues or redirect vectors of public debates.

As observed in the Deliverable 4.3., democratic participation at the level of media systems would manifest through certain qualities and functions such as well-informed citizenship, discussion about issues of the public interest, fostering democratic values, generating some “common ground” that requires both social trust and critique. Systemic factors that support these outcomes revolve around economic, professional, regulatory, political and sociocultural conditions. These were extracted from a large collection of data, mapping the entire spectrum of the news media across various channels, mandates and sources of financing in the 10 EU countries, that was part of task 4.1. and Deliverable 4.2.

Table 1: Factors supporting democratic participation at the systemic media level.

	PUBLIC SERVICE MEDIA	COMMERCIAL MEDIA	NON-PROFIT SECTOR
ECONOMIC	independent and stable funding	plurality of media ownership	plurality of non-profit ownership
	economic transparency	transparency of ownership and financial transparency	transparency of ownership and financial transparency
PROFESSIONAL/ JOURNALISTIC	journalistic standards	journalistic standards	journalistic standards
	institutional and self-regulatory framework - membership in journalistic or professional organisations	institutional and self-regulatory framework - membership in journalistic or professional organisations	institutional and self-regulatory framework - membership in journalistic or professional organisations
LEGAL/ REGULATORY	independent governance and appointment procedures	fair and non-discriminatory support policies (if any)	legal/ regulatory recognition or support of the third sector
POLITICAL	political neutrality	political plurality (diversity of political orientations)	political plurality (diversity of political orientations)
SOCIAL/ CULTURAL	fair representation of social and cultural diversity	inclusive and non-discriminatory approach towards cultural and social groups	giving space and voice to underrepresented communities, particularly minorities

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

Note: If not stated otherwise, in the quantitative analysis, the data on media outlets was calculated altogether within particular sectors (PSM, commercial and non-profit), without division into press, TV, radio and Internet/digital markets.

Following this structure, an assessment of all factors supporting democratic participation was based on a two-step process: the analysis of systemic factors and news production. The analysis of the systemic factors was based on a methodological design developed in the Deliverable 4.2. (Klimkiewicz and Szafrńska, 2024). The news media studied were categorized by their mandate, financing and functions as PSM, commercial/private media and non-profit sector; as well as channels of distribution and mode of production (press, audiovisual, radio and internet/digital) and geographical dimension (national, local/regional). The units of data collection were news media outlets matching the definition provided in the Deliverable 4.2. (Ibidem, p. 9). Therefore, the results presented in this document refer to the state of 2023. Unlike in the case of the PSM and commercial sectors, the samples for local and regional media as well as the non-profit sector included much smaller groups (Ibidem, p. 15). This choice was mostly dictated by availability of relevant data. The list of assessed categories and variables is explained in the Deliverable

4.2. (Klimkiewicz, Szafrńska, 2024, p. 16-17). From these as well as from the categories described in the national reports, economic, professional/journalistic, legal/regulatory, political and social/cultural systemic indicators were selected on the basis of the conceptual framework presented in the Table 1. This framework builds on theoretical considerations regarding the role of the news media in democratic participation presented in many MeDeMAP Deliverables, in particular 2.1 (Carpentier, Wimmer, 2024), 2.2 (Carpentier, Wimmer, 2024c); 3.1 (Seethaler, Beaufort, 2024), 4.2 (Klimkiewicz, Szafrńska, 2024) and 4.3 (Klimkiewicz, Szafrńska, Vanevska, 2025); 5.1 (Kompatsiaris, 2024); 5.2 (Kompatsiaris, Cannizzaro, Miconi, Barile, 2024) and Carpentier and Wimmer (2024b). The analysis of news production was based on a qualitative analysis of interviews with journalists and media producers. A structure of the questionnaire was built around primary and secondary pro-democratic media functions including a provision of accurate information, watchdog and deliberation as well as representation of diversity and political participation (Klimkiewicz, Szafrńska, Vanevska, 2025, p. 9).

2. ECONOMIC FACTORS

Economic factors supporting democratic participation are connected mainly with funding, ownership and transparency. In the PSM sector, where media outlets are either state-owned or publicly owned (e.g. in a form of a foundation, association or public law institution), independent and stable funding is crucial for maintaining a high-quality journalism. In the commercial and non-profit sectors, an adequate plurality of ownership ensures different perspectives on social and political issues, thus also supporting political participation. Transparency of ownership and financial transparency empower users to take well-informed decisions on their sources of information.

2.1. Systemic economic factors

Three economic factors were examined in the first step: sources of funding (for the PSM sector), ownership diversity (for the commercial and non-profit sector) and transparency (for all sectors). As regards the PSM sector, in most countries (as expected) licence or media fees comprise the main source of funding. In a majority of countries this form of basic funding is accompanied by other sources including advertising and sponsorship (most frequent), state subsidies (medium frequent) and sales and subscription (less frequent). In Czechia alone, licence fee is the only source of funding for PSM, while Czechia and Estonia are the only countries where PSM funding is not supported from advertising and sponsorship. On the other hand, Italy, Poland and Slovenia belong to countries with a most 'blended model' of funding. The score categories used for the assessment were distinguished on the basis of occurrence of a particular form of funding in the sample (not the share of particular funding forms in the overall outlets' budgets). These three groups represent three ranges in the scale 0 - 100 percent.

Table 2: Forms of PSM funding in 10 EU countries.

Forms of funding \ Country	Advertising and sponsoring	Sales and subscriptions	Licence, media fees or other forms of public funding	State subsidies, grants	Donations, crowdfunding	Other
Austria	Medium	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
Czechia	Low	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
Estonia	Low	Low	High	High	Low	Low
France	Medium	Low	High	High	Low	Low
Germany	Medium	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
Ireland	Medium	High	High	High	Low	Low
Italy	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Low	Low
Poland	Medium	Medium	High	High	Low	Medium
Portugal	Medium	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
Slovenia	Medium	High	High	High	Low	Low
LEGEND	<p>■ frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>■ medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>■ low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>■ frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>■ medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>■ low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>■ frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>■ medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>■ low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>■ frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>■ medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>■ low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>■ frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>■ medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>■ low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>■ frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>■ medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>■ low occurrence (<33%)</p>

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

The analysis shows a relatively independent and stable source of funding for PSM in most countries (although with a domination of a ‘blended model’), but it is important to add that very much depends on the national context. For example, in Poland, although PSM are funded from licence fees on paper, in reality a crucial portion of funding comes from the state budget “recompensating” insufficient collectability of fees from households. In Ireland, through 2024 PSM faced some deal of uncertainty over the future model of funding as government promises to amend the funding mechanisms have not been fulfilled at the time of writing. In several countries, PSM funding has become quite often politicized.

Ownership diversity in the commercial media sector remains a standard, although not the only factor of a media’s democratic potential. The assessment was based on a share of a dominant market player in each of the following sectors: press (dailies), audiovisual and digital natives. Three levels of risks were attributed to following shares: **high risk** (attributed to markets where two players own more than 40% of the outlets included in a sample), **medium risk** (attributed to markets where two players own between 20% and 40% of the outlets), **low risk** (attributed to markets where two players own less than 20% of the outlets). The data show that the most vulnerable is the press sector - particularly in Austria, Poland and Ireland, while the Italian market, although characterized by a medium risk, is an instance of an oligopolistic system, with more than two large publishing groups having a significant dominance over the ownership structure and media content. The audiovisual sector is highly (Italy, Slovenia) or medium-level (Austria, Czechia, Estonia, Portugal, Poland) concentrated in some countries. The least vulnerable seems to be the digital native sector, although in some countries the risk remains high (Slovenia, Ireland, Estonia).

Figure 1: Ownership diversity on the press markets in 10 EU countries

Ownership diversity on the press market*

- low risk
- medium risk
- high risk
- no data

*Analysis included dailies only

Created with mapchart.net

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

Figure 2: Ownership diversity on the audiovisual news markets in 10 EU countries.

Ownership diversity on the audiovisual market

- low risk
- medium risk
- high risk

Created with mapchart.net

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

Figure 3: Ownership diversity on the digital native news markets in 10 EU countries.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

Media transparency can be considered as a necessary and important condition in each media sector. In the PSM sector, it strengthens and legitimizes the relationship between citizens/users and service providers. In commercial and non-profit sectors, it equips users with a basic knowledge and tools to check and refer to sources of information as well as their reliability and credibility. While transparency is often regulated, it is not always fully implemented in practice. In this sense, not only disclosure of information matters, but also its accessibility and comprehensibility by news users. The analysis in this part focuses on transparency as implemented by media organisations studied in the 10 EU countries. The information was collected on the basis of availability of ownership and financial data on media outlets' websites, as well court or other registers. Three levels of transparency were extracted on the basis of the collected data: **advanced** (attributed to markets where at least two third of the examined outlets in a particular sector show an advanced transparency), **medium** (attributed to markets where at least two third of the examined outlets in a particular sector show a basic transparency) and **low** (attributed to markets where at least two third of the examined outlets in a particular sector show no transparency). Also, the category of “**mixed transparency**” was attributed to conditions where no form of transparency was dominant and various forms occurred side by side.

In the case of the PSM sector, advanced transparency reaches a high level in most of the countries. In Italy, Ireland and Portugal, a mixed model of transparency dominates which means that different outlets functioning within the PSM vary in their model of data disclosure and accessibility (although in all three countries, the majority of the PSM outlets prove an advanced transparency, with a few cases of basic transparency).

Figure 4: Media transparency in the PSM sector in 10 EU countries.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

Figure 5: Media transparency in the commercial sector in 10 EU countries.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

In the largest number of countries (Ireland, Italy, Slovenia) medium level transparency dominates in the commercial media sector. Only three countries (Czechia, Estonia and Portugal) demonstrate an advanced transparency, while France, Austria and Poland display

a mixed model of transparency. Although Germany performs basic transparency on the map, it should be noted that users have easy access to relevant data on ownership and financial data through the KEK reports and databases.

Figure 6: Media transparency in the non-profit sector in 10 EU countries.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

Interestingly, in the non-profit sector, a level of advanced transparency was high in Czechia, Estonia, Germany, France, Portugal and Slovenia, thus in general higher than in the case of commercial sector. Italy demonstrated a medium-level transparency, while Austria, Ireland and Poland showed a mixed model of transparency.

2.2. Economic factors in news production

The second step consists of qualitative assessment of news production based on interviews conducted with journalists and media professionals representing various media sectors. The analysis follows three basic groups of questions. The first refers to primary pro-democratic media functions, including: providing accurate information, watchdog and investigative journalism and creating a forum for the public debate. The second group incorporates two types of practices aiming at representation of societal and cultural diversity and political participation. The third is linked with more general conditions that support or hamper media freedom and pluralism (Klimkiewicz, Szafrńska, Vanevska, 2025).

The table below summarises economic factors reflected in these three aspects of news production.

Table 3: Economic factors reflected in interviewees' accounts on 3 primary functions, representation and participation and conditions for professional journalism.

COUNTRY	3 PRIMARY FUNCTIONS	REPRESENTATION AND PARTICIPATION	CONDITIONS FOR PROFESSIONAL JOURNALISM
AUSTRIA	<p>Investigative journalism (watch-dog function) is suffering due to a lack of financial resources, time, and sufficient staffing</p> <p>Unequal competition between traditional and social media, as the costs of the latter are lower</p>	<p>Participation in the media requires specific organizational structures that can hardly be financed commercially</p> <p>Financial constraints result in a repeated reliance on certain groups or individuals</p> <p>There is lack of resources to cover topics on minorities (with lower interest among audience)</p>	<p>Main concerns regard sufficient resources, the overpowering role of global platforms, and political influences</p> <p>Prioritizing content that attracts larger audiences, constitutes a structural condition that is further amplified by financial circumstances</p> <p>Fewer people have to provide the same output (in-depth research is difficult)</p>
CZECHIA	<p>Lack of resources (both human and financial) is a limiting factor for investigative journalism</p> <p>The influence of media ownership by powerful business figures with political ties affects public trust and media independence</p>	<p>Regional media suffer from underfunding</p> <p>High costs of political participation: it is expensive to provide access to media to anyone who wants to present their message</p>	<p>National media based in Prague compete for people and resources with regional media</p> <p>Financial pressures are particularly strong in the sector of regional media</p> <p>The business model crisis impacts all media</p>
ESTONIA	<p>Investigative journalism is economically demanding, costly and time-consuming</p> <p>Media are affected by economic pressure from global digital platforms and declining print sell</p>	<p>Due to a lack of time or choice, journalists often rely on the same public figures as spokespeople</p> <p>Limited resources for comprehensive coverage</p>	<p>Journalistic standards are shaped by economic pressures</p> <p>The small market suffers from a damaging economic impact of large digital platforms (taking advertising revenues out of the Estonian market)</p>
FRANCE	<p>Investigative journalism became costly and time-consuming</p> <p>Financial concentration in the media poses a threat to plurality</p> <p>The PSM media enjoy autonomy due to financing not subjected to parliament / government</p>	<p>Limited resources impact the technical and human capacity to ensure representation of a wider range of topics and areas</p> <p>A few sporadic attempts to improve employment opportunities for young people, particularly for those from diverse backgrounds, such as descendants of North African immigrants communities</p>	<p>Lack of sufficient financial resources and independence</p> <p>Fear of lawsuits against journalists and newsrooms, which financially weaken the media</p>
GERMANY	<p>Lack of resources is a limiting factor for the investigative journalism</p>	<p>Financial constraints result in a repeated reliance on certain groups or individuals, hindering diversity efforts</p> <p>High living costs in expensive cities discourage</p>	<p>There is a dissonance between fulfilling a mission and making money in independent media</p> <p>PSM journalists enjoy a safer financial situation</p>

		young people without financial support/ destroy diversity in editorial office in non-profit sector	
IRELAND	<p>The movement of advertising to online platforms combined with the lack of adequate government funding has affected all outlets</p> <p>Not enough resources to investigate stories and issues sufficiently deeply</p> <p>Public financial support for court reporting and reporting on local democracy (it was not availed of by most commercial radio stations in 2024 as it was not deemed suitable for their needs)</p>	<p>Lack of resources and time to facilitate the public participation to any great extent.</p> <p>Media management prioritises the production of content for the people who pay</p> <p>The journalism has become the domain of those who are wealthy enough to sustain them throughout low or unpaid internships and a college education. This influences the nature of the content</p>	<p>The loss of valued experienced journalists</p> <p>Fewer people have to provide the same output</p> <p>The trend of people leaving after training and going into other professions because of salary and workload</p>
ITALY	<p>PSM are generally more insulated from economic pressures due to their funding models, private outlets are more vulnerable to financial risks</p> <p>The economic challenges impact ability to deliver in-depth reporting and to conduct investigative journalism</p>	<p>Wealthier political parties and organizations often dominate media access, sidelining smaller or marginalized groups</p> <p>Economic sustainability poses challenges to balanced representation, often limiting the scope for extensive coverage of diverse voices</p>	<p>Censorship in journalism comes from multiple levels of influence, including legal action, usually in economic lawsuits</p> <p>The economic challenges include low salaries, job insecurity, an influence of concentrated ownership</p>
POLAND	<p>Conditions of investigative journalism are steadily deteriorating</p> <p>Devastating competition between editorial offices focuses on the buying of best specialists</p> <p>The local media are impacted by a drastic shortage of staff</p>	<p>Specific legal obligations aimed at reflecting the diversity of the political scene and society in PSM</p> <p>Economic weakness directly affects the lack of editorial independence, which also weakens diversity</p>	<p>Lack of appropriate funding and poor working conditions force young, talented or experienced journalists to leave the profession</p> <p>State media ownership and unfair distribution of state advertising are of a concern</p> <p>The role of the Big Tech and asymmetric dependency on their infrastructures and algorithms poses serious risk</p>
PORTUGAL	<p>Time and financing scarcity are limitations for investigative journalism and barriers to enhancing public debate through journalistic reporting</p> <p>Grants are used mainly by the non-profit sector</p> <p>There is an absence of state supporting measures, besides the long-established</p>	<p>The lack of diversity and representation inside the media organizations - ethnical, gender, age - as a result of scarcity of resources</p>	<p>The lack of sustainable financial models and strategies creates a “vicious circle” of problems influencing the quality and independence of the industry</p> <p>Harsh working conditions nudge professionals to leave due to financial precarity and mental health hazards</p>

	media postal shipping costs paid by the state		Potential court actions, mostly on defamation, which is still a crime, are used as a threat to pressure journalists
SLOVENIA	<p>High costs and lack of time necessary for in-depth investigations are the biggest barriers</p> <p>Community and non-profit media provide improving conditions for investigative journalism, but there is need for applying for grants</p> <p>Financial constraints and understaffing hinder the public debate</p>	<p>Foreign ownership is seen as a supportive condition for ensuring fair representation of political diversity and a check on power</p> <p>Limited resources hamper more adequate representation of cultural diversity in the prime-time news of PSM</p> <p>Limited the ability to compensate minority representatives for their participation in production</p> <p>Lack of available sources leads to repeated reliance on certain groups or individuals, hindering diversity efforts</p>	<p>The reduction or lack of financial resources in all media particularly affects cuts of staff</p> <p>Local correspondent networks across all media are disappearing</p> <p>Younger generations are reluctant to pursue careers in journalism</p> <p>Owners use media outlets as instruments of political and economic interests</p> <p>Dependency on advertisers imposes significant economic pressure</p>

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

In regards to principal pro-democratic functions, financing and adequate funding, particularly, for investigative journalism seems to be a problem everywhere - in all of the countries studied, regardless of media market size and type of media sector (PSM, commercial, non-profit). Economic constraints stem from a **conflict between the news business model and the demanding practice of investigative journalism**. As addressed by a German editor representing digital native sector:

“...it's getting more and more difficult because investigative journalism usually costs more than it brings in at the end. (...) It may have a big impact and lead to change, but what the company can actually earn from it is often not that much more than from a normal, reactive article about the European Championships...” (DE-C-4).

Importantly, in view of some interviewees, financial support for investigative journalism and other content that is valuable from a democratic participation perspective, tends to decrease over years. As observed by a Slovenian interviewee:

“The conditions for journalists to have the time, the room for maneuver, the editorial support, and the financial support to (...) check things out on the ground have deteriorated dramatically over the last 15 years (...) The mantra of the owners is clickbait journalism and quick-buck journalism” (SI-C-3).

A possible antidote mentioned by an interviewee from Portugal is funding investigative journalism from grant schemes. But also in such case, conditions of potential support schemes matter:

“(...) for investigative journalism because it's much more expensive to do. (...) to produce a story that goes through all these methods of work, you need a lot of time. And where is the payment for this time? There's no payment (...). And then you can go after grants,

scholarships. But also grants and scholarships they have their own restrictions, eligibility criteria” (PT-J-3).

As regards participation and representation, interviewees in some countries observed a phenomenon that could be identified as “**structural elitism of journalism**”. In Ireland, interviewees expressed disgust or disappointment that journalism has become “the domain of the children of those who are wealthy enough to sustain them throughout low or unpaid internships and a college education” (EI-C-4). Structural elitism of journalism is a structural phenomenon in a sense that it emerges from certain systemic conditions (news business model and employment related with it), but which manifests in a more complex way - for example, in accessibility and inclusiveness of sources and subjects of coverage, as well as users. In Italy, e.g. wealthier political parties and organizations dominate media access, sidelining smaller or marginalized groups. Also, as observed in Ireland, content is adjusted for those who pay for it. In a similar vein, in Austria prioritizing content that attracts larger audiences constitutes a structural condition that is further amplified by financial circumstances. Structural elitism of journalism is balanced in some countries with PSM policies. For example, an interviewee from France observed that scholarship schemes help young journalists from less privileged backgrounds to enter the profession: “(...) and we see different profiles of young reporters arriving, we really hear them on the air, we hear names that we did not hear 10 years, 20 years ago, so that is very good (...)” (FR-J-1). When it comes to community and non-profit media sector relying on a great deal of voluntarism and engagement of communities, increasing pressures and challenges that potential journalists face due to rising costs of living and economic instability, amplify volatility of the whole sector. As put by an interviewee from Germany:

“Another factor that massively hinders diversity here is (...) the expensive city [Munich is the city with the highest cost of living in Germany], so we can actually work with students very rarely because of the voluntary work (...) the students come or people come along and would like to take part, but then they are eaten up between various deadlines and having to find money to pay the rent themselves” (DE-C-6).

As regards overall conditions affecting media freedom and pluralism, interviewees in several countries mention various forms of economic pressure. First and foremost, is an overpowering role of the Big Tech and their impact on advertising market (Estonia, Poland and Ireland) and shortage of revenues. A Czech interviewee observed that the business model crisis in media has been in place for more than ten years: “(...) where there is no revenue, there are no funds for expenses. That means there’s no money to provide quality resources for journalists or even a decent living standard” (CZ-C-4). In Poland, several interviewees describe difficulties to reach a copyright agreement with the platforms, while “there is also an issue of using our content, for example, to provide information, to train their algorithms” (PL-J-4). Monopolisation of content distribution by platform operators practically leads to unfair competition and disruption in advertising markets, with particular vulnerability of local media in this process (PL-J-5). Another form of economic pressure mentioned, particularly in France and Italy are legal suits. High costs of legal actions and engagement, needed to undergo these obstacles, weakens everyday journalistic practice. As put by a French interviewee: “if you wanted to be visible and what Mediapart [one of the most prominent investigative media in France] does, they throw out articles and they have threats of lawsuits every morning. You have to have super strong backs to do that. It takes time to deal with these lawsuits and it’s expensive” (FR-C-

4-2). Journalists in several countries (Poland, Portugal) refer to harsh working conditions and overtasking. An Irish interviewee notes:

“(…) journalists are being asked to multitask and to do written and social media pieces as well as what’s broadcast that they aren’t paid much more money, but they’re asked to do many more things to keep everything ticking over and going” (IE-C-6).

State media ownership and state advertising structurally influencing economic conditions on the whole media market was mentioned as a problem in some countries (e.g. Poland), interviewees in others pointed out commercial influence from owners (France, Czech Republic).

To summarise economic factors: the conducted analysis has shown that PSM funding, despite occasional uncertainties and political pressures, is based in all countries on a relatively stable funding predominately coming from media fees. As regards diversity of ownership, the most vulnerable vis-à-vis the concentration is the press sector (particularly in Poland and Ireland), while audiovisual sector is highly (Italy) or medium-level (Czechia, Estonia, Poland) concentrated in some countries. The least vulnerable seems to be the digital native sector, although in some countries the risk remains high (Slovenia, Ireland). Interestingly, media transparency achieved the highest level in the PSM sector, a relatively high in the non-profit sector and medium in the commercial sector.

The analysis of economic factors in news production revealed certain structural phenomena that could be observed in all countries - these include in particular **structural elitism of journalism** and a **complex impact of the Big Tech** on media business models, revenues and through these, on journalistic production. The countries with stronger PSM (France, Germany, Austria) have capacities to balance both these phenomena, while countries with less autonomous PSM (Poland, Italy) seem to be more exposed to these trends. Also, importantly, while the business model crisis amplified by the Big Tech has been in place already for a decade or more, the media and journalists themselves, particularly in the commercial sector were pressed to look for alternative sources of funding for themselves, without a major role of public institutions.

3. PROFESSIONAL AND JOURNALISTIC FACTORS

Professional/journalistic factors supporting democratic participation are connected mainly with standards and production guidelines structuring everyday news production routines, as well as they are linked with some level of institutionalization of the profession, which usually manifests in membership in journalistic organisations. Although non-profit media occupy a special place in this regard often relying on a great deal of voluntarism and non-professional involvement, journalistic standards, particularly those linked to epistemic values, are part of their every-day work. Also, in all the sectors, a higher transparency of journalistic standards and their public exposure contributes to pro-democratic values in journalism. Likewise, a higher level of membership in journalistic organisations, as well as consensus on their standards and authority manifest a higher level of professionalism.

3.1. Systemic professional factors

An assessment of professional factors supporting democratic participation was based on collection of data and calculating the percentage of the examined media, for which references to any journalistic standard or membership in a professional organization were identified. The table below represents the result of the assessment. The score categories used for the assessment represent three ranges in the scale 0 - 100 percent and denote a level of occurrence of information about journalistic standards or membership: high (66-100%), medium (34-65%) and low (0-33%).

Table 4: Systemic professional factors in 10 EU countries.

COUNTRY	INDICATOR*	PSM	COMMERCIAL SECTOR	NON-PROFIT SECTOR
		Rate		
AUSTRIA	Journalistic standards	High	High	High
	Membership	High	High	High
CZECHIA	Journalistic standards	High	Medium	Low
	Membership	High	Low	Low
ESTONIA	Journalistic standards	High	High	High
	Membership	High	High	Low
FRANCE	Journalistic standards	High	Low	Low
	Membership	High	High	NDA
GERMANY	Journalistic standards	High	High	High
	Membership	High	Medium	High
IRELAND	Journalistic standards	High	High	High
	Membership	High	Medium	Medium
ITALY	Journalistic standards	High	High	High
	Membership	High	Medium	NDA
POLAND	Journalistic standards	High	Low	Low
	Membership	High	Medium	Low
PORTUGAL	Journalistic standards	High	High	High
	Membership	High	NDA	Low
SLOVENIA	Journalistic standards	High	Medium	High
	Membership	High	Medium	Medium

Note: The provided indicators/rates represent the percentage of the examined media, for which references to any standards / membership were identified, related to the whole sample. Rates: 0-33% for low; 34-65% for medium; 66-100% for high.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

Sharing of information about journalistic standards appeared to be a frequent practice in examined PSM in all countries. The below figure demonstrates a high occurrence of standard sharing with users on PSM websites in all studied countries.

Figure 7: Sharing of information on the news production standards in PSM in 10 EU countries.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

In the commercial sector, sharing of information on the news production standards proved to be less common and widely shared in some countries. Particularly in France and Poland, the proportion of news media organisations sharing journalistic standards with their users stood relatively low. In Czechia and Slovenia, this proportion reached a medium level, and in all remaining countries (Austria, Germany, Estonia, Ireland, Italy and Portugal) stood high in the commercial sector.

Figure 8: Sharing of information on the news production standards in the commercial sector in 10 EU countries.

Sharing information on the news production standards within the commercial sector

- high level (66-100%)
- medium level (34-65%)
- low level (0-33%)

Created with mapchart.net

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

In the non-profit sector, a percentage of news media organisations sharing production standards with users reached a relatively high level in a similar number of countries (Austria, Germany, Estonia Ireland, Italy, Portugal, Slovenia), while in three countries - Czechia, France and Poland - the number of relevant news organisations proved to be rather low.

Figure 9: Sharing of information on the news production standards in the non-profit sector in 10 EU countries.

Sharing information on the news production standards within the non-profit sector

- high level (66-100%)
- medium level (34-65%)
- low level (0-33%)

Created with mapchart.net

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

Membership in journalistic organisations proved fairly high in studied PSM in all 10 EU countries.

Figure 10: Membership in journalistic organisations in PSM in 10 EU countries.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

In the commercial sector, data on membership in journalistic organisations prove more varied. In most studied countries (Germany, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Slovenia), the percentage of news media outlets that either are members of journalistic organisations or their workers belong to such structures stood at the medium level, in Czechia it was low, and Austria, Estonia and France - high.

Figure 11: Membership in journalistic organisations in the commercial sector in 10 EU countries.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

In the non-profit sector, the membership in journalistic organizations seems to be far less frequent practice, particularly in some countries. A low level of membership in this sector was detected in Czechia, Estonia, Poland and Portugal. In Ireland and Slovenia, it stood at a medium level, and in Austria and Germany - at a high level. Yet it should be noted that journalistic organizations primarily target employed journalists who make their living from journalism and specifically represent their interests. In the non-profit sector, particularly community media, a journalistic involvement is often a voluntary, thus non-paid activity.

Figure 12: Membership in journalistic organisations in the non-profit sector in 10 EU countries.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

3.2. Professional/journalistic factors in news production

Qualitative assessment of the impact of professional/journalistic factors on democratic participation followed the analysis of: primary pro-democratic media functions; representation of societal and cultural diversity and political participation; and reflection on a more general conditions that support or hamper media freedom and pluralism.

The table below summarises professional factors reflected in these three aspects of news production.

Table 5: Professional/journalistic factors reflected in interviewees’ accounts on 3 primary functions, representation and participation and conditions for professional journalism.

	3 PRIMARY FUNCTIONS	REPRESENTATION AND PARTICIPATION	CONDITIONS FOR PROFESSIONAL JOURNALISM
AUSTRIA	<p>Fact-checking (also internal fact-checking) and transparency as the ultimate benchmark for conveying information in all media</p> <p>Counteracting disinformation and fake news as a crucial aspect of the legitimization of journalism</p> <p>The task of professional journalism is to report on</p>	<p>Transferring public forum activities to the field of social media (Twitter/X debates, forums on Facebook and Instagram) by private-commercial media</p> <p>Representing diversity as a legal and societal obligation in the case of PBS</p> <p>Especially, community media try to appeal to people who</p>	<p>Commercial broadcasters decline membership in the Press Council due to their unwillingness to commit to supplementary self-regulation</p> <p>All media have established internal processes to monitor compliance with standards</p> <p>Journalists with the necessary capabilities and knowledge</p>

	facts and organize them	might otherwise be less able to make themselves heard	are difficult to find Unequal competition between traditional and social media, the latter are in no way subject to the same regulations as traditional media
CZECHIA	<p>Importance of the information and sources verification, relying on multiple sources</p> <p>Strict editorial system</p> <p>Fact-checking and transparency as the ultimate benchmark for conveying information in all media</p> <p>The declining importance of news reporting in local media</p>	<p>The awareness of the media's role in facilitating public participation</p> <p>Representing diversity as a legal and societal obligation in the case of PBS</p> <p>Selection and diversity of those involved in public debate in the media strengthens the forum function</p> <p>Gender diversity is considered to be far removed from being achieved by all media</p>	<p>Investigative journalism in the editorial office as a source of pride for journalists</p> <p>Lack of resources (professional journalists and money) as a limiting factor</p> <p>Regulatory role of the state, which protects journalists, but with emphasis on its legitimacy</p> <p>Three trends as crisis phenomena: the business model crisis, the concentration crisis of media (with media being in the hands of a small group of investors), and the populism crisis with, in particular, the attacks on public service media</p>
ESTONIA	<p>Work according to the principles formulated in the Estonian Code of Journalistic Ethics and internal editorial standards in some media</p> <p>Fact-checking, balance, giving all parties a voice, keeping facts and opinions separate as firm standards of journalistic work</p> <p>A critical approach to sources</p> <p>Dealing with social trends that are detrimental to democracy (polarization, growing distrust, spread of disinformation)</p>	<p>Lack of anonymity in small towns makes whistleblowing difficult</p> <p>Working in diverse teams, which also continues having Russian-language departments and regional correspondents with access to local people</p> <p>Developing special formats in connection with elections, organizing public debates in the local communities</p> <p>Limited resources for comprehensive coverage and a shortage of female opinion leaders</p>	<p>Collaboration between journalists, both within an organization and between different ones</p> <p>The indirect influence of the owners of media companies on the selection and coverage of topics</p> <p>Investigative journalism being costly and time-consuming.</p> <p>The damaging impact of social media echo chambers on users</p> <p>The damaging economic impact of large digital platforms (taking advertising revenues out of the Estonian market)</p>
FRANCE	A strong standard of honesty, transparency, fact-checking and verification of sources' credibility	Private broadcasting media organizing meetings between the candidates and the citizens before elections	<p>The vigilance to avoid lawsuits - both news and investigative journalism</p> <p>Speed as a factor negatively</p>

	<p>Cross-checking and using at least two sources to confirm information</p> <p>Investigating as a fundamental role of journalism for democracy</p> <p>Paying more attention to debunking fake news spread on social media and by traditional media</p> <p>Media as a key to explaining and facilitating access to reality</p>	<p>Community media as representatives of unrepresented social groups/minorities</p> <p>Legal and ethical obligation for audiovisual media to balance time given to particular parties during election periods and to report the percentage of women invited to the air</p> <p>Franco-centered newsrooms and dearth of journalists representing cultural diversity</p>	<p>affecting the quality and accuracy of news coverage</p> <p>Investigative journalism being costly and time-consuming</p> <p>Social media as an important threat to media freedom and professional journalism (speed, disinformation, fragmentation of the audience, etc.)</p> <p>Fragmentation of the audience</p>
GERMANY	<p>High importance of guidelines imposed by the outside regulatory institution and (in case of commercial broadcasters) own internal standards</p> <p>Importance of using multiple sources and fact-checking</p> <p>Journalism as arbitrator, mediator and orientator in the polarized and information-overloaded society</p>	<p>Presence of whistleblower portals</p> <p>Organizing meetings between the candidates and the citizens before elections at both local (PSM) and national (private media) level</p> <p>Internal obligations for diversity of employees in the private media</p> <p>Lack of specific standards for representing diversity in some media</p>	<p>Lack of resources and time as a limiting factor for the investigative journalism</p> <p>The role of journalism as a contributor to safeguarding democracy through access to information</p> <p>Unrealistic expectations towards journalism among social media users and oversupply of information</p> <p>AI as a fuelling factor in spreading misinformation</p>
IRELAND	<p>Importance of fact checking and of the verification of sources and of information</p> <p>Impartiality as an ideal inscribed in journalism's nature</p> <p>Noticeable importance of standards or guidelines imposed by the outside regulatory institution</p>	<p>Some media encouraging the public to participate in the debate on social media</p> <p>Community media facilitating public participation in news production</p> <p>A dominance of male professionals in newsrooms, an absence of the working class, immigrants, people of colour and women</p> <p>Lack of resources and time to facilitate the public participation to any great extent</p>	<p>Limited access to media literacy and the growing influence of social media in spreading fake news, especially in the case of working-class and of immigrant audiences</p> <p>Journalists receiving threats from investigated actors</p> <p>The vigilance to avoid lawsuits</p> <p>Staff and financial shortages as a limitation for reporting and investigative journalism</p> <p>Enjoying freedom of work</p> <p>A sufficient level of support and defence by the public opinion and media outlets</p>
ITALY	<p>Use of multiple sources and sources verification</p>	<p>Private TV and community media organising debates between experts and the</p>	<p>The endorsement of the audiences as a supportive factor for digital-native media</p>

	<p>A strong role of fact-checking and attempts to combat fake news</p> <p>Gathering information from conflicting sources by digital native outlets</p> <p>Low interest in the investigative journalism by PSM</p> <p>Promoting transparency, ethical guidelines, fact-checking and media literacy</p>	<p>public</p> <p>A strong influence of audience ratings on the choice of topics and guests</p> <p>A declared commitment to cultural and political diversity (i.e., inviting politicians and journalists from across the spectrum)</p> <p>High coverage of elections, including debates, with a strong emphasis on involving women (“No Woman, No Panel” rule)</p>	<p>and local media to carry out investigations</p> <p>Censorship, political pressure and legal threats as common obstacles to investigative journalism</p> <p>A strong social polarization and high level of misinformation</p> <p>Community media participation in civil rights movements</p> <p>Online misinformation and the use of AI in creating it as sources of polarization</p> <p>Low salaries and stressful working conditions</p>
POLAND	<p>Importance of critical evaluation of sources, journalistic integrity and source verification (indicating a primary source)</p> <p>Investigative practice as a tool for real influence on those in power</p> <p>Importance of asking politicians difficult questions</p> <p>Journalistic mission - not only to inform, but also to show the context, background</p> <p>Responsiveness to media users</p>	<p>The need to be a platform for the discussion between different groups, while avoiding support of any side of the political stage</p> <p>Specific legal obligations to reflect the diversity of the political stage and society in PSM (monthly emission quotas)</p> <p>The importance of organizing the debates, giving the voice to female experts or allowing all sides of the political spectrum to express their views</p> <p>Active coverage of the electoral processes (non-partisan media, able to hold politicians accountable for their actions)</p>	<p>The weakening position of investigative journalism due to lack of resources</p> <p>Growing legal (SLAPPs and defamation cases under the controversial Article 212 of the Criminal Code) and financial pressures (dependence on Big Tech)</p> <p>Lack of appropriate funding and poor working conditions discourage entry into the profession</p> <p>An unprecedented scale of disinformation as the greatest risk</p> <p>Lack of sufficient preparation to deal with AI-produced content</p> <p>Problem of information echo chambers</p>
PORTUGAL	<p>A crucial role of internal fact-checking</p> <p>Transparency of sources: reaching a primary source of information and cross-checking</p> <p>Primacy of legal and deontological standards</p>	<p>The threat of “availability bias” (dearth of resources and the contemporary speed of production)</p> <p>Insufficient collaboration with civil society organisations</p> <p>Pro-turnout content, electoral debates and political</p>	<p>Speed of reporting and competition with social platforms negatively affecting the quality of content</p> <p>Staff and financial shortages as a limitation for reporting and investigative journalism</p> <p>Centralisation of journalism</p>

	<p>established in the constitution and laws</p> <p>Journalists are competing for authority with politicians, due to later communicating with citizens directly via social media</p> <p>The technologies seen as a double-edged sword</p>	<p>reporting before elections</p> <p>Attempts to provide immigrants with the journalistic education and the possibility to publish</p> <p>Ethical, gender, age, etc., diversity and representation in the media need to be improved</p>	<p>with a focus on Lisbon</p> <p>Presence of lawsuits and court cases initiated by people under investigations</p> <p>Lack of restrictions or censorship for journalists</p> <p>Lack of appropriate media literacy</p>
SLOVENIA	<p>Verification processes, commitment to accuracy and reliability remain central.</p> <p>Referring to the Slovenian Journalists' Code of Ethics</p> <p>Importance of promptly correcting mistakes and critically assessing sources</p> <p>The requirement of balanced political representation in the public service media has occasionally been misused for justifying political pressures</p>	<p>Effort to include women in discussions</p> <p>Mission to encourage people to vote (especially young people, e.g. using podcasts)</p> <p>Importance of engaging with the local environment in facilitating political participation</p> <p>Openness for civil society organizations</p> <p>Prioritizing content likely to attract a larger audience rather than responding to the needs of a minority</p>	<p>Journalists experience restrictions on access to public information or attempts of political actors to influence investigative journalism in line with their interests (even more intense in regional and local markets)</p> <p>Challenges arise from time constraints and the growing volume of content</p> <p>Financial cuts and largely reduced number of journalists</p> <p>The importance of credibility of a national news agency reporting essential to maintaining other media journalistic standards and public trust</p>

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

As regards the impact of journalistic factors on principal pro-democratic functions, there was a significant consistency across countries and different segments of media markets. Most interviewees emphasized a crucial role of evidence behind news coverage, achieved by source verification and fact-checking. In some cases, interviewees underlined a need to verify sources' credibility and cross-checking (France), a necessity of using multiple sources (Germany, Italy, France), critical evaluation of sources (Austria, Slovenia, Poland), indication of a primary source of information (Portugal, Poland) or a prompt correction mistakes (Slovenia). As put by an interviewee from Austria:

“(…) My aim is to be able to back up every thesis I put forward. Either with a quote or a statistic. In the best-case scenario, I can also contradict statements made by a panelist that are not true” (AT-J-2).

In other words, all presented facts need to be matched with checkable evidence, which journalists are to share if necessary. Also, media users should be informed if full evidence is missing. In words of a German interviewee: “Factual claims must be proven - and ambiguities and uncertainties should be openly stated as such” (DE-J-4). A Polish interviewee mentions three ‘golden’ professional standards: “Journalistic integrity, giving

voice to the other side and [using] double, sometimes triple sources. If I were to point out three most important things, these would be them” (PL-C-4).

Professional factors rely very much on a collective dimension and consensus: editorial checking and the role of common journalistic standards and self-regulatory procedures. There are, however, differences among countries. Some newsrooms operate as “sluices”, where checking takes place at different levels. As explained by an Estonian interviewee: “We have different layers of editors, there are people who proofread first, there are day editors who come in later, then there are language editors” (EE-C-1). Interviewees in some countries refer to a guiding role of self-regulatory codes of conduct or ethics (Germany, Estonia, Slovenia). Respondents in Germany and Ireland emphasize a high importance of guidelines imposed by external regulatory institutions.

In a matter of representation and participation, interviewees generally focus on standards and strategies they use in their newsrooms. Some journalists emphasize an importance of a diverse workforce and climate of openness to discuss various issues. In words of a journalist from Germany:

“I think an open climate in the editorial office, when it comes to political diversity, that people are not punished if they have a different opinion, that they feel they can say it. And when it comes to gender diversity or migrant perspectives, I want to say that everything is encouraged. I think you have to force the editorial team to do more” (DE-J-3).

Including of a variety of perspectives is seen as ‘professionally important’ also by an Irish editor:

“At our news desk, we’d be conscious of including the voices of a minority in Ireland. And whether that’s tweaking our story idea to make sure that we’re including those voices, I think that’s really important” (IE-C-3).

At the same time, there are unwritten or unspoken rules that guide practices in some newsrooms that exclude greater diversity. A French journalist shares that

“(…) the only sociocultural diversity that interests media like mine is very French. They like everything that is French, everything that is very traditional” (FR-J-2).

In view of some other interviewees, an absence of codified rules ensures real openness in covering ‘diversity as it is’. As put by an Italian journalist:

“We don’t have codified strategies or standard procedures. (...) We try to portray cultural and political diversity as it is.(...) We have never placed any veto on any political culture, except for fascist culture” (IT-J-4).

A similar argument is raised by a Polish journalist:

“There are issues of tolerance, openness, understanding towards diversity, lack of prejudice - this is crucial to us. But I also do not have the feeling that this should be additionally written down somewhere in some code, it just happens on its own” (PL-C-4).

It is worth to add, that in the sector of community media, particularly in some countries (e.g. Ireland), participation of the public takes ‘a natural form’ of news production, thus the way news journalism is practiced results in a more diverse representation.

Finally, as regards reflection on more general conditions that support or hamper media freedom and pluralism, many interviewees refer to the role of the Big Tech, algorithms and AI and the way they impact journalistic professionalism and expectations associated with it. On the one hand, expectations vis-à-vis professional journalists become unrealistic given a high saturation of information environment, on the other hand - AI and algorithm-driven content production potentially kills journalistic independence, as it will always be tied with some interest in covered issues or goals to be pursued (the problem observed by an interviewee from Germany):

“Not surprisingly, climate is one of the main risks in the long term. But for me it was a bit surprising that for the next 2 to 3 years it's the issue of misinformation, which is massively fuelled by AI. To be honest, this is also the biggest threat to journalistic diversity for me, because if in the end only texts are created that a) are either formulated out of clear interests that no longer have the goal of being journalistically independent but pursue clear goals, and b) you work with AI-generated texts that ultimately only regurgitate what information was already there, then these are two points that worry me that this diversity will remain. For me personally, that is the biggest danger” (DE-C-4).

Also, some interviewees refer to an absence of a dialogue between news media and platform operators (Poland), an ability of social media algorithms to limit or even reduce the media's visibility (France) or blocking the media's access to the audience (Germany). Disinformation, and its unprecedented scale, is seen as another principal threat to professional journalism (France, Poland) or a tool of destabilization of social systems and democracy (Austria). At the same time, paradoxically, disinformation was coined as a major justification for journalism's very existence (Austria, Slovenia). While AI is perceived as a fuelling factor in spreading misinformation (Germany, Italy), it also creates a new opportunity for professional journalism that can take leadership in navigating media users towards important and critical issues (Slovenia), offer a sort of “ordering a disorder” (Poland) or promote active citizenship (Slovenia).

Surprisingly, a frequent obstacle hampering information provision that many interviewees mentioned was a threat of lawsuits (Ireland, France, Italy, Portugal). Particularly in Poland, interviewees mentioned SLAPPs, defamation cases under the controversial Article 212 of the Criminal Code and lawsuits used as instruments against journalistic critique.

There are, however, not always external factors, that impact professionalism. In view of a French journalist, there is a greater need for transparency and accountability: “what feeds distrust towards journalists is the fact that we are not transparent enough” (FR-J-1). It is also important to add that interviewees clearly link news media performance with epistemic grounding, in a sense of building a more comprehensive and synthesized understanding of current events that potentially empowers citizens. A Polish journalist justifies it with the following words:

“In my opinion, the media's task today is to organize the world we live in, to organize the chaos, to always ask ourselves questions like ‘Why am I writing and what will be the result of this text?’ (...) Thus the point is not only to inform, but also to show the context, background, carefully consider what users really need, what the news is telling about a city, Poland, the world, China, economy, oil prices, etc.” (PL-J-3).

Professional journalism, often put in contrast with disinformation and social media content, is also seen as a counterweight to growing dissonance, political uncertainty and concerns about national and global security. In words of a Portuguese journalist:

“I think that the role of journalists in contemporary societies, particularly ours in Portugal, is to help combat polarisation and disinformation and to help citizens make their decisions and form their convictions based on the best possible information” (PT-J-2).

Thus, professional journalism faces unprecedented handling with complexity where epistemic qualities of democracies are to be defended and human needs for information and communication respected against polarizing divides.

To summarise professional/journalistic factors: the conducted analysis has shown that two attributes studied in all 10 EU countries (membership in journalistic organisations, sharing information about professional standards) proved to be high in the PSM sector. In the commercial sector, both attributes varied across countries, while in the non-profit sector, particularly membership seemed to be least frequent. The analysis of professional/journalistic factors in news production has shown a significant consistency across countries and different segments of media markets. Most interviewees emphasized a **crucial role of evidence behind news coverage**, achieved by source verification and fact-checking. The differences were observed mainly with regard to self-regulation and necessity of existence of codified standards. In some countries interviewees referred to a guiding role of self-regulatory codes of conduct or ethics (Germany, Estonia, Slovenia), in others (Poland, Italy) they admitted an absence of codified rules. Many interviewees emphasised the role of the **Big Tech, algorithms and AI** and the way they impact journalistic professionalism and expectations associated with it. They also clearly linked news media performance with epistemic grounding, in a sense of building a more comprehensive and synthesized understanding of current events that potentially empowers citizens.

4. LEGAL/REGULATORY FACTORS

Legal and regulatory factors play an important role in shaping the three sectors of media systems. From the perspective of democratic participation, the PSM sector needs guarantees of professional autonomy and editorial independence (e.g. through appointment procedures or conflict-of-interest rules) in addition to financial stability. The commercial sector may potentially benefit from fair, non-discriminatory and transparent rules concerning support policies at the state or local/regional level. For the non-profit sector, there is a need to be legally or regulatory recognized as such (e.g. in some EU countries community media are legally recognized as a specific sector), while also any support policies should be designed and implemented in a fair, non-discriminatory and transparent manner.

4.1. Systemic legal and regulatory factors

As regards the PSM sector, legal and regulatory factors vary across the EU and in many countries they do not guarantee impartial, non-discriminatory and fair appointment procedures. The Media Pluralism Monitor (MPM) 2025 has shown that one of its indicators -

independence of PSM - detected a very high, high or medium-high risk in a majority of countries (Blagojev et al., 2025). Also, a high number of countries scored high or medium-band risks under the sub-indicator PSM governance (Blagojev et al., 2025). Interestingly, the MPM report observed that “no European PSM system exhibits a perfectly balanced combination” of pluralism in the composition of boards and councils and open calls for candidacies that are anchored in merit-based criteria (Ibidem, p. 77). These regulatory conditions demonstrate that despite the stable source of financing and contribution of PSM to journalistic professionalism, particularly as regards adherence to standards, appointment procedures in many countries require fairer and transparent rules.

Figure 13: MPM assessment of independence of PSM in 10 EU countries, 2025.

Source: MPM, CMPF, EUI, 2025.

As regards the commercial sector, key regulatory factors include support schemes (e.g. direct, indirect subsidies, state advertising). The Media Pluralism Monitor (MPM) 2025 observed that most Member States provide some form of direct public funding to the media, with an allocation method normally based on objective criteria such as circulation size, geographic reach, language, or content type (Blagojev et al., 2025). This observation was confirmed also by the research including the MeDeMAP countries. The table below shows that some form of state support in the commercial sector is present in most MeDeMAP countries.

Table 6: State support and other forms of funding for commercial media in the MeDeMAP countries.

Forms of funding \ Country	Advertising and sponsoring	Sales and subscriptions	Licence, media fees or other forms of public funding	State subsidies, grants	Donations, crowdfunding	Other
Austria	Orange	Grey	Light Green	Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
Czechia	Yellow	Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
Estonia	Orange	Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
France	Orange	Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
Germany	Orange	Dark Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
Ireland	Orange	Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
Italy	Orange	Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
Poland	Orange	Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
Portugal	Orange	Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Light Grey
Slovenia	Orange	Dark Grey	Light Green	Light Red	Light Grey	Dark Grey
LEGEND	<p>Orange: frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Yellow: medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Light Yellow: low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>Dark Grey: frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Grey: medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Light Grey: low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>Light Green: frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Green: medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Light Green: low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>Red: frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Light Red: medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Light Red: low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>Dark Grey: frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Grey: medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Light Grey: low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>Dark Grey: frequent occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Grey: medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Light Grey: low occurrence (<33%)</p>

Note: The presented data refers to presence of particular funding forms in the media included in a sample, not to level or percentage of given funding forms in the outlets' budgets.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

The countries with the largest scale and occurrence of state support include Austria, France and Slovenia. It is worth to add that according to the data collected, also in France a portion of commercial media receiving some form of donations is quite significant, reaching 12.5%. At the same time, in Ireland, subsidies prove to be more specific and targeted. In 2024, a number of new funds administered by Coimisiún na Meán were designed to support independent journalism (Day and McInerney, 2024). One of these funds aims to support court reporting and reporting on local democracy, while future solutions will support journalism across all three sectors through funding Digital Transformation; News Reporting; Community Media and Media Access and Training (Ibidem). In Poland despite a general lack of support schemes for the commercial media (the only exception are tax reductions for the press), the state has been involved in media ownership, e.g. through owning PAP (Polish Press Agency) and via state-controlled company PKN Orlen owning the Polska Press media group, a large chain of regional/local newspapers and online portals.

As regards the commercial (and also non-profit) sector, the allocation of state advertising stands for one of the most important factors (in many countries) that shapes structural conditions and viability. MPM 2025 assessment found out that only Austria and Portugal (from the MeDeMAP sample) scored in lower risk bands concerning this indicator. The figure below shows other countries with very high risk (Czechia, Estonia, Ireland, Poland), high risk (Italy, Slovenia) and medium-high risk (France).

Figure 14: MPM assessment of distribution of state advertising in 10 EU countries, 2025.

Source: MPM, CMPF, EUI, 2025.

MPM 2025 observed that a small group of countries (e.g. Austria and Italy) have developed legal frameworks or other provisions (such as recommendations, as it is in the case of Slovenia) anchoring the allocation of state advertising in the principle of media pluralism (Blagojev et al., 2025: 73) and editorial independence. Yet it should be added that legal instruments do not guarantee that in practice, state advertising is distributed to media outlets in a plural and transparent manner in some of these countries. Also, given the data provided by the MPM assessment, it should be emphasised that state advertising does not play any role in Germany in the PSM and commercial sectors, while it seems fairly limited in the non-profit sector. This minimal scope does compose a sufficient sample to assess the whole industry.

In the non-profit sector, one of the important regulatory aspects is legal recognition of the non-profit sector. In this regard, MPM 2025 pointed out that in the absence of a legal framework, community media tend to struggle to gain adequate access to infrastructures and funding (Blagojev et al., 2025).

The analysis of data in MeDeMAP countries shows that state subsidies and grants stand for a most widely used form of funding for the sample of non-profit media (in Austria, Czechia, Germany, Ireland and Slovenia), along with donations and crowdfunding most widely provided by users (in Austria, Estonia, Germany, Italy and Slovenia).

Table 7: State support and other forms of funding for non-profit media in the MeDeMAP countries.

Forms of funding \ Country	Advertising and sponsoring	Sales and subscriptions	Licence, media fees other forms of public funding	State subsidies, grants	Donations, crowdfunding	Other
Austria	Medium	Low	High	High	Low	Low
Czechia	Medium	Low	High	High	Low	Low
Estonia	High	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
France	Medium	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
Germany	Medium	Low	High	High	Low	Low
Ireland	High	Low	High	High	Low	Low
Italy	Medium	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
Poland	High	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
Portugal	Medium	Low	High	Low	Low	Low
Slovenia	High	Low	High	High	Low	Low
LEGEND	<p>High occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>High occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>High occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>High occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>High occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Low occurrence (<33%)</p>	<p>High occurrence (>66%)</p> <p>Medium occurrence (34-65%)</p> <p>Low occurrence (<33%)</p>

Note: The presented data refers to presence of particular funding forms in the media included in a sample, not to level or percentage of given funding forms in the outlets' budgets.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

4.2. Legal and regulatory factors in news production

In the case of legal and regulatory factors in news production, the qualitative analysis follows the three sectors (PSM, commercial and non-profit). In the PSM sector, most frequently mentioned legal and regulatory issues and practices included political influences on appointment procedures and regulatory changes. In Austria, for example, an editor observes that in the case of ORF political pressures can manifest through funding or changes in the “composition of the supervisory bodies, changes in the composition of the management, and influence on appointments in the organisation” (AT-C-1). In France, some media professionals articulate the risk of privatization of the public media and political influence through funding and budgeting schemes as the main threats. As put by an interviewee:

“If the money is budgeted, you depend on the willingness of the power in place. Therefore, you will necessarily have to not displease too much if you want your budget to be renewed, it is a real problem of independence of information in relation to the executive power” (FR-J-1).

In Germany, regulatory safeguards for PSM are viewed by some as conditions to maintain institutional spaces for professional journalism. One of the interviewee (DE-J-1) points out, for example, that journalistic profession is already endangered and that the preservation of PSM serves generally to the preservation of journalism. In Poland, some interviewees refer to situation in PSM that were put formally into the state of liquidation by the Civic

Coalition government in December 2023. This radical legal solution was chosen in order to break with the previous PSM staff and performance routines that made PSM's mouthpieces of the previous government. As one interviewee explains:

"I have been working in the public media for a long time - I lived through the times of the previous regime, as I think it should be called, and the worst thing this regime was about, was the imprisonment of the public media, this destruction of the public media, reducing them to the role of a sound mouth and absorbing the words of politicians of the only political option. (...) even though 5 or 6 months have passed since the changes in the public media, some journalists still think that it is propaganda, that someone will come and tell them what to do, they do not feel liberated..." (PL-C-1).

Also, in Slovenia, the new PSM governing model was subject of different political interpretations. For a journalist from the right-wing media outlet, the changes of the management and editorial personnel at public service media RTV Slovenia were a "relatively brutal political purge" (SI-J-4). At the same time, the interviewees from the PSM describe the circumstances after the new governing model as a "relief" and "returning to normality". The PSM editor points out:

"Earlier, we had direct pressure from politics, especially on the news programme, which is the most politically exposed here. [...] And now, the depoliticized governing council is a firewall between this kind of independent public media and politics trying to interfere. It seems to me that the composition of the Council and the whole management structure of the public service broadcaster has helped to bring some relief" (SI-C-1).

In the commercial and non-profit sectors, the most important issues revolved around a fair and proportional allocation of subsidies and state support means. For example, in Austria, the views on how state subsidies to media outlets should be distributed varied. For national newspaper journalists, these should be awarded in a more focused manner and support "professional political and independent journalism and, above all, high-quality journalism" (AT-J-3). In view of professionals from regional newspapers, there is a need of resources that help operate on several platforms (AT-C-5). Community media representatives expect policies that would maintain "democratic political diversity" (AT-C-6). An interesting solution emerges in the segment of private commercial broadcasting, suggesting that licence fee (provided in general for PSM) is to be shared by other media providers. In view of one interviewee:

"Why is it not possible to solve it similarly to the climate ticket for the ÖBB [the Austrian Federal Railways], where I can travel on all means of transport? I could imagine that many people would be prepared to pay 365 euros a year in exchange for being able to read every newspaper in Austria online. I do not have to log in 18 times with any other names" (AT-C-2).

Both in Portugal and Czechia, several interviewees suggest greater government funding as a solution to crisis in business models and professional journalism. In words of one Czech interviewee:

"So, states should step in, just as they support films or national cinema, and create a journalism fund based on clear and transparent principles to support the spectrum from left to right. That way, everyone can find relevant information that still operates within the democratic framework" (CZ-C-4a).

In Poland, a significant role of the state in the media market is of concern. For some interviewees, a risky impact on media pluralism comes with state media ownership (PL-C-4), others emphasise a destructive role of unfair distribution of state advertising. Reliance on state advertising affects a selection of topics (PL-J-6) and selective and arbitrary financing from the state budget impacts market conditions (PL-C-4). Local media seem to be most vulnerable to these pressures (PL-C-5). In addition, the local media suffer from the existence of ‘municipal media’ - outlets published by local authorities and sustained with the public funding. In a description of one interviewee:

“This is not competition, this is killing the independent regional press with distorted pseudo-journalism [...] Almost all local governments have [their own media], it is only a question of whether it is monthly or quarterly. And then the photo of the mayor or the president is on every other page - he opened something here, closed there, and so on” (PL-J-5).

To summarise legal and regulatory factors: the conducted analysis has shown that despite a large degree of variations in legal and regulatory factors among the countries, similar problems emerge. In the PSM sector, legal and regulatory safeguards in many countries do not guarantee impartial, non-discriminatory and fair appointment procedures for PSM management bodies. In the commercial and non-profit sector, state support and subsidies are seen as a necessary solution in targeting crisis in media business (Portugal, Czech Republic). A more targeted or focused distribution of subsidies is welcomed in some countries (Austria, Ireland), while in others there is an issue of state’s involvement in media ownership and state advertising and a necessity to regulate it in a more fair manner (Poland).

5. POLITICAL FACTORS

In normative terms, news media - as the institutions of the public sphere - are expected to provide a space for diversity of opinions and political views in order to enable democratic deliberation and formation of the public opinion. In contemporary hybrid media systems where boundaries between traditional media and digital networks and platforms dissolve, it becomes more difficult to maintain a meaningful diversity of factual political information as information spaces are flooded with manipulative and misinformative content. At the same time, political plurality and right to orientation stand as fundamental standards of liberal democracies.

Each of the three sectors seems to play a slightly different role in an institutional setting: PSM are generally expected to provide moderate internal pluralism of opinions and views, thus in general offering a neutral stance. Commercial media, on the other hand, are to generate political diversity either through external pluralism of diverse political orientations or internal pluralism offering a mixture of diverse views. In practice, this variety or diverse political orientations may result both from autonomous editorial policy, and some form of political influence that can be generated by preferences of audiences, or be the outcome of other form of a more articulated political stance. The commercial media having a particular political orientation are not automatically detrimental to democracy. What causes the risk is political bias and partisanship that result from political clientelism, instrumentalization or capture. In the case of non-profit media sector,

external or internal pluralism is basically generated by the communities involved in production and reflects the inclusiveness of the sector.

5.1. Systemic political factors

The analysis of systemic political factors is based on assessment of political orientations of the news media representing PSM, commercial and non-profit sectors in the MeDeMAP countries. The relevant categories of political orientations were developed and described in the Deliverable 4.2. “Data Set for the Map of EU Media Systems and Country Reports Combining the Results of Task 4.1.” (Klimkiewicz, Szafrńska, 2024). The collected data reflect the situation consistent with the state of knowledge in 2023 and applied to the sample of news media outlets covered by MeDeMAP.

Table 8: Political orientation according to media sectors: PSM, commercial and non-profit sector.

	PSM	COMMERCIAL	NON-PROFIT
AUSTRIA	The PSM demonstrate a central orientation	Around 70% of the examined media outlets prove a far right, right or central right orientation, with only 16% proving a central orientation, and only 6% proving a left orientation*	All examined media prove a left or central left orientation
CZECHIA	NDA	NDA	NDA
ESTONIA	The PSM demonstrate a central orientation	80% of the examined media outlets prove a central orientation, the remaining outlets have a far right, right or central right orientation	Around 79% of examined media outlets prove a central orientation; within the remaining 21% right and left orientations are shared equally
FRANCE	The majority of outlets within the PSM prove a central orientation, with few cases of a central left orientation	Around 46% of the examined media outlets prove a central orientation; within the remaining 54% right and left orientations are shared equally	Around 67% of the examined media prove a far-left, left or central left orientation; 24% of the examined media prove a central orientation
GERMANY	The majority of outlets within the PSM prove a central orientation, there are, however, cases of a central left or central right oriented media	Around 54% of the examined media outlets prove a central orientation, within the remaining 46% right and left orientations are shared equally	Around 63% of the examined media outlets prove a central orientation; within the remaining group, a left orientation is dominant
IRELAND	The PSM demonstrate a central orientation	Around 48% of the examined media prove a far right, right or central right orientation; around 37% prove a central orientation	Around 48% of the examined media outlets prove a left or central left orientation, with 25% having central right or right orientation and only 22% proving a central orientation
ITALY	The PSM demonstrate a central orientation	Around 35% of the examined media prove a far right, right or central right orientation, and 29% prove a far left, left or central left orientation, with only 23% proving a central orientation	A dominance of a left or central left orientation (69%) of the examined media, with few cases of a central orientation and no cases of a right orientation
POLAND	After changes within the PMS, right-wing orientation was displaced with middle left	Around 39% of the examined media outlets prove a far-right, right or central right orientation, with 33% prove a central orientation, and 27% prove a far-left, left or central left orientation	Around 64% of the examined media outlets prove a central orientation; within the remaining 36% right and left orientations are shared equally

PORTUGAL	The PSM proves a neutral orientation	A dominance of the central orientation, with only 2 cases of a right orientation and 1 case of left orientation	Around 52% of the examined media prove a central orientation, and 42% prove a far-left, left or central left orientation, with few cases of a right orientation
SLOVENIA	The PSM proves a neutral orientation	Around 46% of the examined media outlets prove a central orientation	Around 26% of the examined media outlets prove a central orientation, with another 26% proving a far-left or left orientation and no outlets with a right orientation

* If any of the percentages provided in the table do not add up to 100%, it indicates that there was data missing in the sample.

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

As regards the PSM sector, public service media in most countries demonstrate a centre orientation, which generally reflects normative expectations in terms of internal pluralism. There are, however, exceptions. In France, the majority of outlets within the PSM demonstrate a central orientation, with few outlets - in particular on the regional TV and radio market - reflecting a centre left orientation. In Poland, after PSM governance changes in 2023, a right-wing orientation was replaced with a centre left orientation. Still, the appointment changes, which resulted in an adjustment of editorial line, were not paired with necessary legal and regulatory remedies that are necessary to secure the PSM remit and professional autonomy. PSM in Italy underwent significant changes in 2023 and 2024, leading to decline of journalistic independence, politicisation and unprecedented level of political pressure (see more: Blagojev et al., 2025; Article 19, 2025). All the examples show that PSM remain vulnerable in some countries to political pressures. Once politically inspired partisanship takes place, it becomes far more difficult to reinstate internal pluralism as a democratically stable solution.

Table 9: Political orientation in the PSM sector.

Country \ Political orientation	Far left	Left	Moderate / centre left	Centre	Neutral	Moderate / Centre right	Right	Far right
Austria	low	low	low	frequent	low	low	low	low
Czechia	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data	no data
Estonia	low	low	low	frequent	low	low	low	low
France	low	low	medium	frequent	low	low	low	low
Germany	low	low	low	frequent	low	low	low	low
Ireland	low	low	low	frequent	low	low	low	low
Italy	low	low	low	frequent	low	low	low	low
Poland	low	low	frequent	low	low	frequent	low	low
Portugal	low	low	low	low	frequent	low	low	low
Slovenia	low	low	low	low	frequent	low	low	low

Legend:

- frequent occurrence (>66%)
- medium occurrence (34-65%)
- low occurrence (<33%)
- no data

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

In the commercial sector, the situation varies from country to country and depends on a segment of the market (press, audiovisual, radio and digital). In general, most countries

gravitate towards moderate external political pluralism, while some countries demonstrate polarised external political pluralism (Italy, Poland). In France, the overall media landscape remains relatively balanced with a centre-left orientation in the press and digital segments, but recent trends point to an increasing right-wing shift in parts of the audiovisual sector, particularly among privately owned channels. Austria displays a more clearly right-leaning orientation, while in Ireland the commercial radio market tends to lean similarly. Across Europe, political orientations are often historically rooted and institutionally relatively stable, but can also evolve over time with ownership changes and shifting journalistic cultures.

Table 10: Political orientation in the commercial media sector.

Country \ Political orientation		Far left	Left	Moderate / central left	Centre	Neutral	Moderate / Centre right	Right	Far right
Austria	Press						■		
	Audiovisual				■				
	Radio						■		
	Internet and digital						■		
Czechia	Press	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	Audiovisual	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	Radio	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	Internet and digital	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
Estonia	Press				■				
	Audiovisual				■				
	Radio				■				
	Internet and digital				■				
France	Press				■				
	Audiovisual						■		
	Radio				■				
	Internet and digital				■				
Germany	Press				■				
	Audiovisual				■				
	Radio				■				
	Internet and digital				■				
Ireland	Press				■				
	Audiovisual								
	Radio						■		
	Internet and digital								
Italy	Press				■				
	Audiovisual							■	
	Radio				■				
	Internet and digital			■					
Poland	Press						■		
	Audiovisual				■				
	Radio				■				
	Internet and digital				■				
Portugal	Press				■				
	Audiovisual				■				
	Radio				■				
	Internet and digital				■				
Slovenia	Press					■			
	Audiovisual					■			
	Radio					■			
	Internet and digital				■				

Legend:

- frequent occurrence (>66%)
- medium occurrence (34-65%)
- low occurrence (<33%)
- no data

Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

5.2. Political Factors in media production

As in previous parts, the basis for an assessment of political factors in media production were interviews conducted with journalists and editors in all three sectors. The table below summarises political issues in four relevant aspects of the qualitative analysis: providing a forum for the political debate, representation of a political diversity, political participation and conditions for journalism and democracy.

Table 11: Political aspects of news production.

	FORUM FOR A POLITICAL DEBATE	REPRESENTATION OF POLITICAL DIVERSITY	POLITICAL PARTICIPATION	CONDITIONS FOR JOURNALISM AND DEMOCRACY
AUSTRIA	<p>Forum for public debate restricted mostly to the debate between public figures</p> <p>Social media content is based on algorithms that limit political messages</p> <p>Politicians threatening with power or an advertising boycott as a tool to intimidate the media</p> <p>Disinformation and fake news used by politicians, also as tools to attack the media</p>	<p>The trend to avoid the debate in the political context influences the “invitation policy” of the media</p> <p>Independent media are no longer needed by politicians who organize their own media coverage</p>	<p>In public and private media, the focus is mainly on processes of representative democracy, such as elections and referendums</p> <p>Some political powers, especially on the right-wing spectrum, use social media to spread content in a very targeted way</p> <p>A critical approach to offering media space by editorial offices (especially to political extreme movements)</p>	<p>The dangers posed by digitalization and global platforms, and political influences</p> <p>The need to guarantee media independence through internal mechanisms that defend journalists from political attacks and protect them from making “too many concessions” to the powerful</p>
CZECHIA	<p>Editorial cooperation as a basis for a professional approach to politics in public debate</p> <p>Community media as a space for the expression of those who do not have a political platform, giving a voice to politically marginalized persons and groups</p>	<p>Introducing political diversity, even if the social desirability effect could be high</p> <p>Refusing to publish statements by right-wing extremist politicians/parties in particular, resulted in political diversity not being achieved</p>	<p>Journalists’ awareness of the media’s role in facilitating public participation</p> <p>Diversity of political representatives invited to the media as a tool for making political participation more attractive to recipients</p> <p>In many media, the communication platform is most often handed over to politicians</p>	<p>A visible crisis related to media concentration (in the hands of a small group of investors) and a crisis of populism in media, with particular emphasis on attacks on public media</p> <p>Strict, journalistic standards (also related to quality education) are crucial</p>
ESTONIA	<p>Developing special formats in connection with elections, organizing public debates in the local communities, national</p>	<p>Due to a lack of time or choice, journalists often rely on the same public figures as spokespeople</p> <p>Whoever is currently</p>	<p>Lack of anonymity in small towns makes whistleblowing difficult</p> <p>Conviction that sharing information</p>	<p>The emphasis is on empowering citizens to participate actively in the democratic process, rather than acting as authority figures who instruct the public on</p>

	<p>broadcasters travel across the country to facilitate regional political discussions</p> <p>Commercial media has stepped back from some aspects of political coverage</p> <p>The public broadcaster is the only one that has maintained comprehensive election coverage</p>	<p>in power inevitably receives more attention from the media</p>	<p>with users supports their participation in political processes and helps them to understand the actions of their representatives</p> <p>Many state institutions are no longer physically present in smaller areas and there are no representatives to speak to</p>	<p>how to think or behave</p> <p>Estonia's government actively counters propaganda through media literacy programs</p> <p>High level of media freedom in Estonia</p> <p>The polarisation of society, growing mistrust, and the spread of disinformation are detrimental to democracy</p>
FRANCE	<p>PSM limitation in the diversity of the public debate they facilitate: the relatively homogeneous nature of their audience may impede the intended exchange of opposing viewpoints</p> <p>The regulations established by ARCOM identified as a fundamental and rigorous framework for audiovisual media</p>	<p>The fundamental requirement to uphold the representation of political diversity in a manner consistent with the prevailing national political context and with the electoral outcomes of political parties</p> <p>Limitations exist in non-audiovisual media regarding the representation of political 'extremes'</p> <p>Non-audiovisual media have no accountability with regard to political issues</p>	<p>Information fatigue and public disinterest</p> <p>The media serving as an independent forum for expressing criticism of the government is crucial for effective political participation</p>	<p>Emergence of the far-right movements and their influence on the media</p> <p>Lack of independence as a main challenge for performing democratic functions by the media</p> <p>The representation of political diversity is presented as one of the standards integrated into journalism training</p> <p>A growing significance of fact-checking and media literacy in the context of the political independence of the media and their users</p>
GERMANY	<p>The growing influence of extreme right-wing narratives perceived as one of the greatest concerns</p> <p>Concerns whether promoting debate should be the media's responsibility or if politicians should better fulfil their own (communication) duties</p>	<p>Balance in reporting (presenting the arguments of both sides), leaving out extremisms</p> <p>Polarized audience, leading to aggressive postings on particularly controversial topics in the media's channels</p>	<p>Presence of whistleblower portals</p> <p>Organizing meetings between the candidates and the citizens before elections at both local (PSM) and national (private media) level</p>	<p>A limited role of journalism due to organizations and politicians communicating with citizens directly via social media. The anti-democratic endeavours of some parties and media</p> <p>The need to defend the media against right-wing authoritarian tendencies</p>
IRELAND	<p>Providing a forum for public debate interpreted most often in terms of issues surrounding coverage of national and local elections rather than facilitating actual</p>	<p>Importance of standards or guidelines imposed by the outside regulatory institution</p> <p>The composition of the editorial board may influence the</p>	<p>Some media encouraging the public to participate in the debate on social media</p> <p>Informing on election or political issues rather than eliciting</p>	<p>Avoiding contact with journalists by politicians, unless they want to push their own agenda</p> <p>Being independent of political parties as the most important feature</p>

	<p>debate and discussion</p> <p>Impartiality as an ideal inscribed in journalism's nature</p>	<p>political bias of the media (lack of working class representatives)</p>	<p>actual debate and discussion</p>	<p>of journalism in democracy</p> <p>Limited access to media literacy and the growing influence of social media in spreading fake news, especially in the case of working-class and of immigrant audiences</p>
ITALY	<p>The strong political alignments of certain press outlets shape their discourse</p> <p>Wealthier political parties and organizations often dominate media access, sidelining smaller or marginalized groups</p> <p>Polarization tends to frame debates in binary terms - either for or against - stifling nuanced dialogue and limiting constructive engagement</p>	<p>Governing parties often receive more coverage due to their activities; efforts are made to include politicians from across the spectrum</p> <p>In the case of the press, the editorial direction is often shaped by the outlet's political stance, leaving limited room for differing perspectives outside specific sections</p>	<p>PSM committed to political participation through comprehensive coverage of elections, including live debates and collaborations with institutions</p> <p>Editorial teams characterized by gender balance, fostering coverage of women's rights and related issues, thus supporting more inclusive political participation</p>	<p>Maintaining independent reporting by resisting pressures from advertisers and political influences</p> <p>Promoting transparency through ethical guidelines</p> <p>Conflicts of interest due to media concentration among a few powerful groups</p> <p>Political interference, especially in the press sector</p>
POLAND	<p>Media's crucial role of being a platform for the discussion between different groups, while avoiding support of any side of the political stage</p> <p>Investigative practice as a tool for real influence on those in power</p> <p>Importance of asking politicians difficult questions</p>	<p>The degree of political representation in the media related to the support political parties received in the last elections</p> <p>Specific legal obligations to reflect the diversity of the political stage and society in PSM</p>	<p>The important role of the media in engaging audiences politically, but maintaining distance and objectivity of the content</p> <p>A decreasing will of politicians to speak with the media</p> <p>Active coverage of the electoral processes is crucial</p> <p>Local and non-profit media sectors pay more attention to representation and integration</p>	<p>Unresolved legal or procedural issues that could limit political or economic pressure</p> <p>A significant role of the state in the media market</p> <p>The key task of journalists - both to reflect and shape the perception of democracy and its usefulness for the society</p> <p>Financial problems of the media translate into their vulnerability to various political influences</p>
PORTUGAL	<p>The balance in the representation of all political powers is secured by providing voice, media space, coverage and debating rights to all the parties</p> <p>Journalists are competing for</p>	<p>Political diversity is seen as a widely practised branch of diversity</p> <p>Giving a voice to diverse political actors, regardless of popularity or size</p>	<p>Facilitation of political participation as a possible outcome of journalists' work</p> <p>Linking the increase of turnout in the parliamentary elections with the debates provided by</p>	<p>The media professionals are not concerned with the political pressure on journalism</p> <p>Despite the media freedom, the threat of lawsuits against authors by people covered in their stories is present</p>

	authority with politicians, due to later communicating with citizens directly via social media		broadcasters	Freedom of speech in the country is “total”
SLOVENIA	<p>Restrictive access to public information in practice.</p> <p>Political actors influencing investigative journalism in line with their interests (revealing certain information)</p> <p>Examples of receiving instructions from media owners to limit coverage of specific political figures or parties</p>	<p>The significance of the role of media in ensuring diverse political representation</p> <p>A policy of presenting opposing views from the government and the opposition</p> <p>Foreign ownership is seen as a supportive condition for ensuring fair representation of political diversity</p>	<p>Mission to encourage people to vote (especially young people, e.g. using podcasts)</p> <p>Importance of engaging with the local environment in facilitating political participation</p>	<p>Media ownership concentration identified as a key structural issue undermining democratic function of the media</p> <p>Political pressure (under right-wing governments), particularly on public media, is widely considered a major threat to media freedom and professional journalism</p> <p>Threat to media freedom arising from antagonistic divisions in media community fuelled by political actors and their clientelistic connections with media owners</p>

Source: MeDeMAP, 20255

As regards a creation of a forum for the political debate, in many countries editorial cooperation or consensus plays important roles in deciding how this process takes place. For example, in Germany, there is a concern about growing influence of extreme right-wing narratives perceived as one of the greatest threats in the sound public debate. As put by a German editor:

“We see it as our task to allow almost the entire political spectrum to have their say. There are indeed a few exceptions. For example, we have made a decision in our editorial department, we do not conduct interviews with parties that are being monitored by the Federal Office for the Protection of the Constitution...” (DE-C-4).

In media with a high level of audience participation (in particular radio), it is the audience that navigates a course of debates, and in these circumstances, the discussions might lack necessary political diversity. As explained by a French journalist:

“The limit is that it is our listeners who call, so you have an expression which necessarily reflects our listeners who are, rather teachers, professors, rather CSP+ [higher social classes]...” (FR-J-1).

In some countries, journalists and editors observe that commercial media have stepped back from some aspects of political coverage and only PSM provide a comprehensive coverage of electoral debates (e.g. in Estonia). In the case of others, particularly TV debates play important roles. A journalist from Portugal reports:

“Portugal is probably the country that holds the most TV debates at election time. Dozens of debates, some from pooling the most important television channels” (PT-C-1) In countries with a greater degree of political polarisation (e.g. Italy, Poland), the

debates gravitate towards political orientation of a given medium. In words of an Italian journalist:

“...[In] a newspaper with a fairly precise political stance, I might indicate as a risk the fact that on certain topics there is a bit of alignment of opinions” (IT-C-3).

In terms of representation of political diversity, journalists and media workers have to find a right balance between mitigating political pressures for greater visibility and on the other hand, clarify opaque or obscure aspects of active politics. For example in Slovenia, journalists of a regional medium were instructed to “support a specific political option to come to power” and not mention “other options” (SI-J-5). In Poland, journalists found politicians, officials and decision-makers to obscure “certain things, to make it quieter, to make it calmer so that people do not find out certain things so that something is unclear” (PL-C-2). Hence, the journalists should bring a greater clarity and understanding. Yet, traditional journalism, as some observe, is not anymore important for politicians who can build their visibility and communication with voters directly via social media. As observed by an Austrian journalist:

“... politically, as I said, the biggest threat is that they no longer need us. And I think the antidote can only be to say how you’re not going to make too many concessions to keep them with you” (AT-J-2).

Composing diverse political representation seems to be for some a matter of principle and common sense, for others also a regulatory obligation. As expressed by an editor from the Czech PSM:

“...we approach the political currents in the Czech Republic by following the principle of graded equality, which sounds a bit ambivalent, but it’s that the equality isn’t absolute, but it’s graded, meaning that everyone has the opportunity to get some space, but the space should correspond appropriately to the significance of the political currents they represent in the country” (CZ-C-1).

In a similar vein, a Portuguese journalist points out that:

“If we have a story about the government, centre-right, it’s not mandatory that we also have a story about centre-left. It’s the story of interest in that week, a matter of common sense. We don’t have strict diversity guidelines” (PT-C-3).

The Polish journalist, on the other hand, stresses the importance of accountability and regulatory obligation:

“...we are accountable for how much airtime we give to each party. And in this respect, the rules are such that [it should be] equal when it comes to those parties that are in parliament. It is known that it usually comes down to using, I would say, percentages, which are also related to the support that these parties received in the last elections” (PL-J-1).

Most interviewees tend to associate political participation with elections, vote turnout and electoral campaigns. For example, in the case of Austria, interviewees mention concentration on elections and referendums and see these as part of democratic processes. Estonian interviewees point to special electoral formats such as organizing public debates in the local communities and travels of national broadcasters across the country aiming at facilitating regional political discussions. High coverage of elections,

including debates, with a strong emphasis on involving women, mark practices of Italian media. German respondents underline meetings between the candidates and the citizens before elections at both local (PSM) and national (private media) level. All these initiatives sought to encourage citizens to get involved in politics and electoral process. As put by a Polish interviewee:

“We can - and, above all, we want to - strengthen democracy and social participation because we know that turnout in every election is important and, as we witnessed, it has shown that turnout can actually win elections. We have the tools to influence this” (PL-C-1).

For a Slovenian editor, political participation paves the way through emancipation, through inclusion of problems, topics, and groups that could be omitted without media’s commitment:

“We involve people in asking the authorities about certain problems that concern them. And in this way we try to maintain this social tension, inclusion, emancipation. To keep the emancipatory potential in the community” (SI-C-3).

In general, political participation seemed to benefit from legal and ethical obligations imposed on audiovisual media in order to balance time given to particular parties during election periods (France, Slovenia) as well as from news media encouraging the public to participate in the debate on social media (Ireland).

As regards conditions for journalism and democracy, some interviewees see the state as an important actor balancing media and political power of private owners. As articulated by a Czech journalist:

“As for political power (...) they [politicians] still see the media as being there to interpret what they said the way they wanted it said. So, states should step in...” (CZ-C-4a).

On the other hand, journalists e.g. in Poland, refer to a significant role of the state in the media market that potentially affects media freedom through structural conditions, including state advertising. Structural conditions, particularly concentration of ownership and clientelistic relations, were also mentioned in the case of Slovenia.

In some cases, political pressure is perceived as one of the greatest threat to democracies, particularly when it comes to influencing certain media and their output. For example, in Austria concerns are raised about influences on PSM. As put by an Austrian editor:

“... the greatest danger comes from politicians and political parties who try to restrict free media. In the case of ORF, this can happen through changes in funding, changes in the composition of the supervisory bodies, changes in the composition of the management, and influence on appointments in the organization” (AT-C-1).

A French journalist depicts the intricate relationship between politicians deciding about funding/budgets and journalists in a more subtle way, but still uncovering dependencies:

“...If the money is budgeted you depend on the unwillingness of the power in place, therefore you will necessarily have to not displease too much if you want your budget to be renewed, it is a real problem of independence of information in relation to the executive power” (FR-J-1).

Yet, a voice from a Portuguese journalist shows that the relationship between politicians and media workers might be very different in other countries:

“We are in a good position. We do our journalism in peace. So we’re not that bothered with political powers, and that gives you room to do your job” (PT-C.2-3).

To summarise political factors: the analysis has shown that political factors remain of utmost importance for all sectors, and in some cases decisive about their viability. At the systemic level, the analysis has shown that PSM in most countries demonstrate a centre orientation, which generally reflects normative expectations in terms of internal pluralism. In the commercial sector, most countries gravitate towards moderate external political pluralism, while some countries demonstrate polarised external political pluralism, at least in some sectors (Italy, Poland). France, by contrast, maintains an overall balanced media landscape, with a centre-left orientation in the press and digital sectors, and a growing rightward shift within parts of the audiovisual market, particularly among private broadcasters. With reference to political aspects of news production, the media’s role in facilitating political debate is influenced by the editorial consensus of the newsroom and external rules or principles. In countries with a greater degree of political polarisation (e.g. Italy, Poland), the debates gravitate towards political orientation of a given medium. In terms of representation of political diversity, journalists and media workers tend to seek a right balance between political pressures for greater visibility and investigating opaque aspects of active politics. This effort is seen by some as a matter of principle and common sense, others are also guided by regulatory obligations. Political participation in general is discerned through participation in election, electoral politics and voting. At the same time, some pointed also to the processual character of participation, that may be strengthened through emancipation and inclusion, and weakened through exclusion of topics, problems and groups. Finally, as regards conditions for journalism and democracy in the political context, interviewees paid attention to other actors such as state, private owners and a necessity to balance power and influences of those through the involvement of independent media.

6. CULTURAL FACTORS

In normative terms, cultural factors are connected with expression and representation of culture in and through media systems and news production. This refers to the ability of the news media and news contents to reflect in an open manner social actors and groups with various cultural backgrounds, their needs and interests, and also fundamental views on social and political reality, including cultural values and traditions. This aspect of democratic participation is linked with communication rights, particularly a right to commonality, in other words a right to participate in one’s own culture, language, the right of individuals and communities to have their stories and views heard.

6.1. Systemic cultural factors

Research on systemic cultural factors was reflected in the MeDeMAP project in the analysis of the third - **non-profit / community media sector** in all 10 countries. As results have

shown non-profit sectors in some countries benefited from legal recognition (Ireland, Austria, Germany), stable and systemic financial support from public sources (Austria, Germany), public support for associative student media and media literacy or a lively segment of an alternative press (France). Overall conditions of the sector were also positively affected by the existence of bodies/institutions grouping community media (Austria), non-profit investigative media offering transparency and adherence to high journalistic standards (Slovenia, Poland) (Klimkiewicz, Szafrńska, 2024).

The weaknesses, on the other hand, included: lack of legal recognition or very limited legal recognition of the third sector (Czech Republic, Poland, Estonia), overall weakness of the third/non-profit sector (Estonia, Poland, Czech Republic), lack of financial support for the third sector or community media with the exception of some minority media (Czech Republic, Poland, Estonia), limited access to media production for minorities - mainly due to lack of or limited recognition of national and ethnic minorities (Germany, France) (Klimkiewicz, Szafrńska, 2024).

A common example of thriving non-profit activities includes running independent media initiatives, many of them focusing on investigative journalism, fact-checking and in-depth, slow reporting. A number of such activities have been frequently developed by journalists leaving established newsrooms in order to advance crowdfunding-based projects. Such initiatives are observed, in greater or lesser extent, in all researched countries, which shows a common need in the journalist community to self-organize and redirect models of journalism that would counteract negative trends like a growing spread of disinformation and clickbait-based news reporting. On the other hand, some signs of politicization of the third sector media can be noticed, too. For instance, in Poland and Italy, religious non-profit radio stations are highly politically involved while benefiting from direct or indirect state subsidies. In Estonia and Slovenia, many municipal media outlets serve as a support tool for local politicians instead of keeping local authorities accountable for their words and actions.

These results may be compared with two indicators developed by MPM 2025. The indicator on Representation of minorities in the media that combines both legal safeguards supporting minorities access to the media as well as practice, reveals a great variety across the countries. Among the MeDeMAP countries low risk countries included Germany and Estonia; low medium risk countries Czech Republic, Poland, Italy; high medium risk countries Ireland, France, Austria and high risk countries Slovenia and Portugal.

Figure 15: Representation of minorities¹ in the media in 10 MeDeMAP countries, 2025.

Source: MPM, CMPF, EUI, 2025.

The cross-country comparison shows that the involvement of PSM in representation of minorities plays an important role. As observed by Blagojev et al. (2025), the representation of legally recognised minorities is usually guaranteed by public service media in most countries, despite some differences in practice. Also, most of the EU member states provide news in minority languages (Blagojev et al., 2025), at least for some legally recognized minority groups. More problematic, however, seems to be the representation of non-recognised minorities and stability of minority programming in general.

The indicator on Local/regional and community media showed a relatively stable condition of these sectors in some MeDeMAP countries which is congruent with the MeDeMAP results (Germany, Italy, Austria - low risk countries). The group of low medium risk countries included Ireland, France, Poland; high medium risk countries Slovenia and Estonia and high risk countries Portugal and Czech Republic.

¹ For the purpose of the MPM, minority is defined as a cultural or social group:

- numerically inferior to the rest of the population of a state,
- smaller than the majority group in the respective country,
- in a non-dominant position,
- whose members possess ethnic, religious or linguistic characteristics differing from those of the rest of the population.

MPM also uses the term “legally recognised minorities”, which refers to national minorities recognised by the law. The minorities which are not recognized by the law are specified as “non recognised minorities” (CMPF, 2025).

Figure 16: Local/regional and community media in 10 MeDeMAP countries, 2025.

Source: MPM, CMPF, EUI, 2025.

As observed by (Palmer & Seethaler, 2025) the main issue affecting community media in Europe remains the lack of an adequate and up-to-date legal framework to favour their development and long-term stability. According to Blagojev et al. (2025: 84) eleven EU member states have still not legally recognised community media. In addition to the lack of recognition, the absence of a legal framework causes also a struggle for gaining adequate access to infrastructures, funding, professional training and privileges.

6.2. Cultural Factors in News Production

The table below summarises cultural factors in news production in the three of studied sectors: PSM, commercial media and non-profit sector

Table 12: Cultural factors in news production.

	PSM	COMMERCIAL MEDIA	NON-PROFIT SECTOR
AUSTRIA	<p>The importance of including critical voices in reporting, but with an awareness of false-balance debate (giving voice to controversial views)</p> <p>Legal obligation to represent cultural/social diversity</p> <p>Household fee that makes PSM financing possible</p>	<p>Debates about different cultures and the coexistence of cultures are well covered</p> <p>Strong focus on a broader background when recruiting and making new appointments in some editorial teams</p> <p>More diversity seen as tapping into new target groups and reaching a broader audience</p>	<p>Adherence to the Austrian Press Council is observed across all community radio and tv outlets, with its Code being an integral component of the binding</p> <p>Attempts to keep editorial offices strictly out of the mainstream, to devote attention to marginalized topics</p> <p>Taking care not to discriminate against anyone or any population groups</p>
CZECHIA	<p>Representing diversity as a legal and societal obligation in the case of PBS</p> <p>Efforts to ensure representation of minorities in editorial teams</p> <p>Attempts to address topics that might not be mainstream, but concern a smaller group of the population</p>	<p>Representatives of different ethnicities in the editorial teams</p> <p>Examples of creating internal ethical codes, which require giving a voice to people who are not represented in the media</p> <p>Prioritization of the main currents dominates over other determinants and weakens diversity</p>	<p>Main news focus on the minority community, their successes and problems</p> <p>Some media are included in the Independent Journalism Foundation, with clearly set rules that the editorial teams must follow</p>
ESTONIA	<p>Lack of official limitations or quotas. In some media, internal standards regarding diversity are present</p> <p>Building awareness in journalists' community of how diverse audiences are served as important practice. Strategic editorial building</p> <p>Creating some kind of separate formats to provide diversity (different topics, different languages)</p>	<p>Building awareness and responsibility of journalists, without percentage analyses or official working methods</p> <p>The biggest limitation is language (Estonian-language radio must and can only be in Estonian)</p> <p>Taking care of women's representation in the media (women are less willing to act as experts and guests in the media / it is more difficult for them to decide to work in the media)</p>	<p>Building awareness and responsibility of journalists, without written principles</p> <p>Resource (time, money) are a constraint</p> <p>Minority issues do not attract wider attention and do not reach a wider audience</p> <p>Striving to make it as easy as possible for people to report their problems and concerns</p>

FRANCE	<p>Obligation to submit reports to ARCOM concerning the degree of parity achieved on air</p> <p>Efforts to recruit women as experts. Women present in the editorial team to a high degree</p>	<p>Recommendation to submit reports to ARCOM concerning the degree of parity achieved on air (not for the press)</p> <p>Franco-centred attitude of some media as an obstacle to diversity</p>	<p>The effort to ensure a plurality of actors and points of view responds to an editorial strategy of the media</p> <p>Resource constraints affect the limited possibilities of representation (equipment and team members shortages)</p> <p>Actively building diversity of the editorial team through internships and placements with people from diverse backgrounds</p>
GERMANY	<p>Diversity in the workforce and cultivating a corresponding, corporate culture</p> <p>Official commitments to implement diversity included in documents (State Treaty for Broadcasting and Telemedia)</p> <p>The presence of diversity projects to raise awareness</p>	<p>Balance in reporting as the key to success</p> <p>Encouraging journalists to promote more migrant or female perspectives to be heard, even despite difficulties</p> <p>Drawing attention to problems that are overlooked and require publicity to be noticed in the mainstream</p>	<p>Language skills (German's dominance) as a barrier to reaching different groups and their topics</p> <p>Resource shortages (human resources, money, time) limit the possibilities of taking care of diversity</p> <p>The key is being attentive and scrutinizing. Moving away from the marketing logic of clickbait headlines</p>
IRELAND	<p>Some public service media are driven by ratings, just as commercial entities are and this undermines diversity</p> <p>Linguistic diversity as a core part of diversity</p> <p>Limited understanding of diversity, marginalization</p>	<p>The nature of the composition of most newsrooms lacks diversity and is described as "pale, male and stale"</p> <p>This sustains a mainstreaming effect of middle class, centre or centre right opinions and perspectives</p> <p>Commercial broadcasters aim at making money out of content, so minority programming is ignored as not generating income</p>	<p>Journalistic ethos understood as seeking out and wanting to have pluralism of voice, diversity of topic</p> <p>Reflecting social diversity in the team as a key activity</p> <p>A responsibility of the media to be countering social media echo chambers (as a threat to diversity)</p>
ITALY	<p>Efforts are made to feature journalists from diverse backgrounds, which ensures that the public encounters a range of perspectives</p> <p>A relatively supportive environment for journalists promoting diversity</p> <p>Strong commitment to</p>	<p>Editorial teams are frequently composed of individuals from homogenous backgrounds, which limits the diversity of perspectives and experiences brought to the newsroom</p> <p>Lack of formal policies on gender or cultural diversity</p>	<p>Importance of increasing representation within newsrooms</p> <p>Need for formal journalism education. Financial constraints and tensions arise from their role as watchdogs</p> <p>Active participation in civil rights movements and</p>

	<p>inclusivity, frequently featuring diverse political facts, minority viewpoints, and cultural perspectives</p>	<p>Diversity ‘naturally’ emerges in coverage of conflicts and civil rights issues, though without a strategic effort to institutionalize these values</p>	<p>advocating for underrepresented groups, using their platforms to amplify marginalized voices and promote equality</p>
POLAND	<p>Creating specialized channels/messages for minorities and marginalized groups as a realization of the so-called media mission</p> <p>Striving for gender balance in the editorial team, despite difficulties (in finding female experts)</p>	<p>There are no codified rules regarding reflecting the diversity in private newsrooms</p> <p>Creating of internal codes in some editorial teams</p> <p>The journalistic mission and internal conviction that it is an important part of journalism as a factor supporting diversity</p> <p>Fewer opportunities for media expression for residents of small towns (lack of correspondents, poor local media, niche topics)</p>	<p>Building awareness and responsibility of journalists, without written principles</p> <p>The internal codes in some newsrooms</p> <p>The multidimensional diversity of the editorial team as an internal expression of supporting diversity and guaranteeing a better perspective on marginalized topics</p>
PORTUGAL	<p>The PSM remit mandates diversity</p> <p>Presence of profiled channels/messages targeted at minorities</p> <p>The key thing is diversity in the editorial team itself</p> <p>Careful content construction (quotas), taking into account multi-faceted diversity distinguishes public media from others</p>	<p>Gender diversity is the general practice at the newsroom level. Women are often in the majority. Women are underrepresented in leadership positions. Nationality diversity: the growing Brazilian and African communities are somewhat represented at the TV reporter level and with a few anchors</p> <p>Valuable initiatives such as providing journalistic education to several immigrant journalists or the joint work with journalists outside of Europe</p> <p>Lack of codified principles of approach to diversity, use of different strategies depending on the editorial office</p>	<p>Potential of alliances with the mainstream media</p> <p>Media with clearer focus than the mainstream. Because of its specific operational model, it can add to diversity by accompanying the instant coverage of day-to-day events with more targeted slow projects</p> <p>Citizen journalism is not legally recognised</p>

SLOVENIA	Professional norms and the Code of Ethics of Journalists as a key guiding tool Special programs for specific minorities Striving for more representation of women in television programmes	Professional norms and the Code of Ethics of Journalists as a key guiding tool Particular social groups only get attention when there are events with negative connotations Good coverage of the NGO sector	Professional norms and the Code of Ethics of Journalists as a key guiding tool Giving the direct voice to the minorities. Giving broadcasts to these communities Encouraging women to work in the newsroom Ethnically diverse teams
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Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

As regards the Public Service Media, representation of cultural diversity seems more structured than in other sectors, but the practice seems to depend much on the newsrooms and awareness of journalists.

The interviewees in some countries noted that cultural reporting (including minorities) is not only PSM’s legal obligation, but also social obligation (e.g. Austria). A Czech interviewee observes that PSM reporting may not focus on mainstream [groups or issues] but may “concern a smaller group of the population” (CZ-C-1). Still, interviewees in some countries complain that PSM is too much tied by following ratings. In the words of an Irish journalist:

“But both RTE and Virgin will be very much driven by ratings, like they’re both commercial animals” (IE-C-1).

In addition to manoeuvring between high ratings’ expectations and representation of non-mainstream groups and issues, PSM face dilemmas in composing their newsroom and editorial teams. The German interviewee emphasises good employment conditions can contribute to quality and diversity of reporting: “...more important is to have editorial teams with well-trained people who also have a bit of time for their work and then you can do a lot with them, even if they may not belong to the group affected by this topic themselves” (DE-J-1).

In terms of delivering diversity, an interviewee in Poland, for example, compares more structured regulatory conditions for political diversity (proportions and quota for fair representation of political parties) against an absence of such requirements for cultural and social diversity: “...when it comes to, for example, gender or some other factors, there are no quotas” (PL-J-1). On the other hand, a Slovenian editor from PSM observes that “We have set ourselves the goal of monitoring the proportion of women in all news programmes and to do a monthly analysis...” (SI-C-1).

For a Portuguese journalist, a care to represent gender equality and ethnic diversity “is permanent, and it’s not recent” and is a feature “that distinguishes the public radio and television service from the others” (PT-J-1). Other editor points out that representation of diversity “is a work in progress” (PT-C-1).

In the commercial media sector, cultural diversity has mostly been commented from the perspective of editorial team recruitment.

A Czech editor points out that in the newsroom he/she represents there is “a lot of people from other ethnicities. We are very open, and we don’t have this problem” (CZ-C-2). An Estonian editor observes difficulties with recruitment of female professionals: “I was once looking for new columnists. I wrote to five men, four of whom agreed immediately, one said he’d think about it for a moment, and well, one said he didn’t have time. And I think I wrote and phoned and talked through over thirty women. The result was zero” (EE-C-3). Also, an Irish editor saw the composition of the newsroom as decisive in an ability to deliver a more diverse output:

“All our staff are all native Irish, predominantly male... So, I suppose by very nature this would limit your interaction with various cultures unless various groups are getting in touch with us” (IE-C-2).

A similar picture emerges from Italian commercial media. In the words of the interviewee:

“...there are editorial teams composed only of white, bourgeois men. It is difficult to achieve cultural diversity. In Italy, there is only one diversity manager, who is still a white, able-bodied, gay man. It seems a bit lacking” (IT-J-3).

Some journalists notice relevance of internal guidelines and practice. A Polish journalist underlines that:

“we have a number of internal regulations on how to write, how to address sensitive issues related to sexuality, sexual life, issues of faith, gender identity or issues related to nationality, origin, religion. We treat these issues with exceptional seriousness” (PL-J-3).

For a Portuguese journalist, one of the obstacles for delivering cultural diversity is a hectic newsroom culture and a necessity to simplify the process of news collection and editing:

“I think it’s a mixture of things that make bringing this diversity difficult. (...) Many of the newsrooms that I work in, are subject to the pressure of producing and the media times are completely dizzying. And often the first name that comes up in giving and framing a particular subject, is a name that jumps out at everyone and [these] are the names that we remember” (PT-J-2).

At the same time, Portuguese interviewees also mention valuable initiatives such as providing journalistic education to several immigrant journalists or the joint work with journalists outside of Europe.

In Slovenia, on the other side, professional norms and the Code of Ethics of Journalists play an important role as a key guiding tool. Still, the formalized guidelines and rules are missing in the newsrooms and journalists are rather led by intuitive and professional adherence to high standards. In the words of an interviewee: “...compared to the public media, we are quite behind, and we don’t really have a strategy” (SI-J-2).

In the non-profit sector, there is a strong awareness among the journalists in some countries (e.g. Austria, Czech Republic, Ireland) that their reporting and coverage focuses on marginalised topics and issues and also a willingness to bring these more to the forefront of mainstream media and public debate. Interviewees are also aware of barriers that limit access and participation in non-profit journalism (e.g. linguistic barriers in Germany; the problem of invisibility of minority groups in Portugal or financial shortages preventing some minorities to engage in community media in Slovenia). An Estonian interviewee also mentions time constraints and work pressure: “...we don’t have these strategies and principles in writing because we don’t have the time to work on them to

formulate them very much. But we do it all the time based on experience, feeling...” (EE-C-6). In a similar vein, the Polish interviewee observes:

“We do not have written standards, we do not have some kind of regulations, but I have the impression that in us as journalists, there is something that simply could be called a standard written somewhere in us, that we want to show this diversity” (PL-J-6).

An interviewee from Ireland points out to important link between newsroom and society:

“Diversity when it comes to hiring practices is really important, you know, if society is changing, if you’re delivering media it has to be reflected back you know. (...) [A medium] is reflective of society that more people are out and comfortable with, either the gender expression or the sexuality then, so I think those type of things, representation in the media is really important” (IE-J-6).

One feature that distinguishes the non-profit sector in Italy is inclusiveness, as many of these outlets actively champion inclusivity in their coverage, extending this commitment to cultural and gender representation within their content and organizational practices.

To summarise cultural factors: The analysis revealed that at the systemic level, the conditions that support the third sector include: legal recognition, stable and systemic financial support from public sources, an existence of an institutional framework, transparency and adherence to journalistic standards. On the other hand, barriers, additional to legal and financial constraints, include in particular problems with access of minorities to the media, particularly in the commercial sector, due to ‘lack of their visibility’ or recognition of their status. As regards cultural factors in news production, PSM still play a leading role in providing cultural diversity, in some degree because of legal or social obligations, or greater likelihood of achieving more diverse newsrooms than is the case of their commercial counterparts. While interviewees in the commercial sector were well aware of the crucial role of culturally diverse newsrooms in delivering diversity, in practice this condition is rarely met.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the complex role of the news media in shaping democratic participation is affected by an interplay of economic, professional, legal, political, and cultural factors at the systemic level and the level of news production. As observed by Carpentier and Wimmer (2024b, p. 98), a depth and scale of this participation very much depends on whether the media’s pro-democratic roles are restricted to the minimalist definition of “informational and watchdog roles, in combination with a restricted articulation of the forum role, as a ‘marketplace of ideas’” or whether media structures as well production routines are able to activate various forms of participation and representation. The comparative analysis completed in this Deliverable reveals a number of trends that show both potential strengths of pro-democratic participatory attributes as well as salient vulnerabilities at the system and news production levels. The table below offers a brief summary of these according the five categories of factors.

Table 14: A country-based comparison of strengths and weaknesses in five areas of analysis.

FACTORS	WEAKNESSES	STRENGTHS
ECONOMIC	<p>High (Austria, Poland, Ireland) or medium (Germany, Italy, Slovenia) risks to ownership diversity on press markets</p> <p>High (Italy) or medium (Czechia, Estonia, Poland) risks to ownership diversity on audiovisual markets</p> <p>Lack of institutional support: the commercial sector and journalists have been largely left to find solutions without major support from other institutions</p> <p>Negative impact of Big Tech on media business models, revenues, and journalistic production in most countries</p> <p>Underfunding and resource scarcity across all countries and sectors (particularly hinders investigative journalism)</p>	<p>PSM funding based on licence or media fees in most countries</p> <p>Alternative funding sources in all media outlets</p> <p>High transparency in public media (ownership and financial data readily available)</p>
PROFESSIONAL/ JOURNALISTIC	<p>Resource constraints, a lack of adequate funding, staff and time (Czechia, Estonia, Germany, Ireland, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia)</p> <p>Pressure from external actors, e.g. political influence (Slovenia) and legal threats (Ireland, France, Portugal, Poland)</p> <p>Challenges from digitalization, e.g. social media is seen as a major risk due to its speed, spread of disinformation, and the fragmentation of audiences (France, Ireland, Poland)</p> <p>The rise of AI-produced information poses a challenge in combating misinformation (Poland, Italy)</p>	<p>Commitment to professional standards in all countries, e.g. fact-checking (Austria, Czechia, France, Germany, Italy), verifying with the use of multiple sources (Czechia, France, Germany, Italy), and maintaining impartiality (Ireland)</p> <p>Facilitating public participation, e.g. appealing to marginalized voices (Austria, France, Ireland), organizing debates (Germany, France), encouraging voting (Slovenia, Poland)</p> <p>Addressing disinformation as key problem in most countries</p>
LEGAL/ REGULATORY	<p>State involvement in media ownership (Czech Republic, Austria, Ireland, Poland)</p> <p>Lack of guarantees for impartial, non-discriminatory, and fair appointment procedures for PSM governance in many countries</p> <p>Non-transparent allocation of state advertising (a very high risk - Czechia, Estonia, Ireland, and Poland, and a high risk - Germany, Italy, Slovenia)</p>	<p>Importance of ethical guidelines and standards imposed by the outside regulatory institution (Ireland, Germany, Portugal)</p> <p>Targeted support for commercial media (Ireland), state financial support (Austria, France)</p>
POLITICAL	<p>Vulnerability to political influence, high risk of political bias and partisanship (Poland, Slovenia)</p> <p>Skewed political spectrum, lack of a political balanced spectrum in some countries (Austria, Ireland)</p>	<p>Neutrality and central orientation of PSM across most of the countries (Austria, Estonia, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, and Slovenia)</p> <p>External pluralism, diversity of viewpoints, a variety of different political orientations across different outlets</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">SOCIAL/ CULTURAL</p>	<p>Structural elitism of journalism, i.e. the profession may not adequately represent the full spectrum of society (Ireland, Austria)</p> <p>Prioritization of the main currents dominates over other determinants</p> <p>Language barriers as a significant structural impediment to effective inclusion (Estonia, Germany)</p> <p>The dominant cultural/regional orientation in the editorial office and in the content (France, Portugal, Ireland)</p>	<p>Legal and ethical frameworks to ensure the representation of cultural and social diversity in PSM (Austria, Czechia, France) and internal ethical codes in other media (Poland, Slovenia)</p> <p>Proactive diversity initiatives, e.g. specialized channels for minorities (Poland, Portugal, Slovenia) or increasing the representation of women as experts and in editorial teams (France, Slovenia)</p> <p>Strategic recruitment for editorial teams (Austria, Portugal)</p>
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Source: MeDeMAP, 2025.

As can be seen from the sector comparison, PSM consistently emerges as a strong and stable pillar. Its funding, primarily from media fees, is relatively secure, and it scores high on professionalism attributes like membership in journalistic organizations and adherence to professional standards. Countries with more autonomous PSM (like France, Germany, and Austria) are better equipped to counter structural challenges, such as the impact of Big Tech, than those with less autonomous PSM (like Poland and Italy). At the same time, a key vulnerability for PSM lies in legal and regulatory frameworks in all countries, which often fail to guarantee fair and impartial appointment procedures, impacting quality governance. Community and non-profit media - despite facing significant challenges, such as economic instability and the need for legal recognition and sustainable funding - often show higher levels of transparency and provide a platform for underrepresented communities. Their reliance on voluntarism and grants makes them vulnerable, yet they remain vital for fostering pro-democratic media functions and supporting journalistic standards.

Economic factors play a principal role in viability and sustainability of the news media particularly in a long-term perspective. A structural dependence on digital platforms both in terms of findability and distribution translates into financial constraints and vulnerability vis-à-vis the concentration. This has been most exposed in the press sector (particularly in Poland and Ireland), while audiovisual sector remains highly (Italy) or medium (Czechia, Estonia, Poland) concentrated in some countries. The least vulnerable seems to be the digital native sector, although in some countries the risk continues to be high (Slovenia, Ireland). These findings resonate with views of journalists and media producers who pointed to **structural elitism of journalism**, caused also by a shortage of financial resources and a **complex impact of the Big Tech** on media business models, revenues and through these, on journalistic production.

Exposure of professional/journalistic factors seems to be high in the PSM sector, where journalists more frequently adhere to professional standards and organizational memberships. It should be emphasized, however, that in other media sectors, informal or unwritten codes of ethics and journalistic standards are often developed, both in commercial and the non-profit sector. Across all media sectors, the commitment to source verification and fact-checking is deemed paramount; however, the formalization of ethical standards through codified rules varies considerably among different countries.

From a legal and regulatory perspective, a primary challenge for PSM are insufficient legal safeguards guaranteeing fair and impartial appointment procedures for PSM management boards. In the commercial sector, state support and subsidies are seen as vital, although issues of state involvement in media ownership and advertising remain a concern in some countries. A key challenge for the non-profit sector is lack of legal recognition and the absence of a legal framework in some countries, which hinders access to infrastructure and funding. Therefore, fair, non-discriminatory, and transparent support policies are essential for the sector's long-term viability.

Political factors are a dominant force, influencing the viability of all media sectors. While PSM generally maintains a centrist orientation, in the commercial sector most countries gravitate towards moderate external political pluralism, and some countries demonstrate polarised external political pluralism (Italy, Poland). Interviews on media production show that journalists mostly perceive political participation through the lens of election, electoral politics and voting. At the same time, some pointed also to the processual character of participation, that may be strengthened through emancipation and inclusion. It is also important to add that interviewees articulated a necessity to balance power and influences of actors such as state and corporate owners through the involvement of independent media.

In the realm of cultural factors, PSM takes a leading role in promoting diversity, a function often reinforced by legal mandates and a more representative composition of newsrooms. Still, the analysis of both systemic and news production levels shows that access of minorities to the media depends on their legal recognition and status, and thus might be fairly limited. While the commercial media acknowledge the significance of diversity, practical implementation remains a consistent challenge, also because of economic factors.

To conclude, in words of Carpentier and Wimmer (2024b, p. 97) it is “hard to conceive of contemporary democracy” without a diverse and robust news media landscape. This should be composed of strong and independent PSM, the vivid commercial sector equipped with additional safeguards balancing platform dominance (particularly with reference to protection of copyright and original production), and the community media strengthened by legal recognition, institutional and financial support. A sustainable development of all these three sectors is essential for maintaining balance and pluralism within the media ecosystem. The common denominators for all of the sectors remain fight for the epistemic and cognitive foundations of journalism, adaptation to the impact of algorithms and AI, while protecting original and in-house production and the constant need for maintaining autonomy and independence from both political and economic pressures as well as growing political polarization and cultural and social cleavages.

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